

Fakulta rybnářství
a ochrany vod
Faculty of Fisheries
and Protection
of Waters

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2024

Study on the compatibility of germ cells after transplantation into a recipient

Studie kompatibility zárodečných buněk
po transplantaci příjemci

Doctoral thesis

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after transplantation into a recipient

Doctoral thesis by
Rigolin Nayak

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CHAPTER 1

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1. General introduction

Surrogate production in fish offers an enormous opportunity to restore and propagate endangered or commercially valuable species through germ stem cell transplantation into a recipient. Other possible applications may include increasing gamete production or reducing the sexual maturation time. However, the success of surrogate production always depends on factors such as 1) the compatibility of transplanted germ cells with the recipient's gonadal somatic cells, 2) achieving complete sterility of the recipient, 3) choosing the right developmental stage for the transplantation, and 4) selection of suitable germ cell type. The presented thesis thoroughly discusses the germ cell precursors, their development, and the techniques used for surrogate production in Chapter 1. The thesis deals with xenogenic germ stem cell transplantation from a smaller species with a low amount of gametes into a significantly highly fecund larger species (Chapter 2). The epigenetic changes of transplanted germ cells in two kinds of recipients are discussed in Chapter 3. It covers our understanding of the reliability of the surrogate production approach in aquaculture and its future applications. The following chapter deals with the harvesting of viable germ stem cells from two smaller species via partial gonadectomy without sacrificing the donor individuals (Chapter 4). Overall, this thesis provides a thorough understanding of germ stem transplantation with potential experimental studies using three types of freshwater species: Giant danio (*Devario aequipinnatus*), zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), and pearl danio (*Danio albolineatus*). This thesis consists of two published (Chapters 2 and 3) and one unpublished study (Chapter 4).

1.1. Germ cells and their precursor

Germ cells are the only cells that give rise to a whole organism and are responsible for transmitting genetic information between generations. They have a unique potential to self-renew in order to maintain the stem cell population in the gonad and also differentiate to produce either gametes upon meiotic division. The primordial germ cell (PGC) is the origin or precursor of the germline cells, which is set aside from the somatic cells at a very early stage of embryonic division (Wylie, 1999) is the process known as PGC specification and later migrates to the presumptive gonadal anlagen. In this discussion, the author only focuses on the PGC specification and migration in teleost. PGC specification is determined by the maternally derived factors rich in RNA and protein molecules called germ plasm (Xu et al., 2010). PGC localization was described by Yoon et al., who cloned zebrafish *vasa* (now *ddx4*) homologue (*vas*) to analyze the RNA expression in the PGCs (Yoon et al., 1997). Other genes, such as *nanos-1*, *dazl*, and *dead end*, were also discovered to be associated with germplasm (Raz, 2003). In zebrafish, as per the *ddx4* RNA location, the germplasm is first divided into two clumps and located along the cleavage planes at the 2-cell stage embryo, later condenses into four clumps at the 4-cell stage. PGCs are formed before the gastrulation, and their specification occurs at four distinct locations during the 1k-cell stage. PGCs undergo 2-3 mitotic cell division, reaching 25-30 in total cell number before migration (Lubzens et al., 2010). All the cells eventually migrate in the same direction and arrive where the gonad develops (Yoon et al., 1997). PGCs migrate towards the final target with the help of somatic cells that provide the directional cues on the route. The starting position of the PGCs varies among individual embryos and is known to be random with respect to their embryonic axis (Weidinger et al., 1999; Raz, 2003). The ligand stromal-cell-derived factor (SDF)-1a, a CXC subfamily chemokine secreted by the somatic cells, provides the directional cues for PGC migration. SDF-1a interacts with the seven-trans-membrane G protein-coupled receptor CXCR4b. The *cxcr4b* RNA is uniformly distributed in the embryo during the onset of

PGC migration at early gastrulation. Later, at the late gastrulation, the expression is more specific to the PGCs that align along the lateral plate mesoderm of the trunk and the border between the head and the trunk mesoderm and continue expressing during migration until they arrive at the location where the gonad will be formed (Doitsidou et al., 2002). A strong correlation between the position of the PGCs at different stages of their migration and the tissues expressing high levels of *sdf-1a* transcripts was reported by Doitsidou et al., suggesting the essential role of SDF-1a in providing directional information to the migrating PGCs. SDF-1a acts as a natural chemoattractant for zebrafish PGCs. The migrating PGCs are very sensitive to the level of *sdf-1a* expression, allowing their precise migration to the final target (Doitsidou et al., 2002). In addition, a decoy receptor, CXCR7b, is structurally related to CXCR4b (Mahabaleshwar et al., 2008), plays an important role in PGC migration. It acts as an antagonistic and has been reported to play a crucial role in controlling precise temporal and spatial SDF-1a activity in somatic tissues and proper migration of PGCs. The binding of SDF-1a to the CXCR4b receptor activates downstream signaling cascades, leading to cell polarization and directed migration. In contrast, the binding of CXCR7b to SDF-1a in the somatic cells leads to ligand sequestration and lysosomal degradation of SDF-1a (Mahabaleshwar et al., 2008). PGCs migrate towards several intermediate targets before arriving at their final target and encounter different somatic structures that potentially provide directions (Olsen et al., 1997; Yoon et al., 1997). Upon their arrival at the gonadal anlagen, PGCs coalesce with gonadal somatic cells and colonize. Once sexual differentiation occurs, germ cells in male and female gonads take different paths. Eggs are produced in the female after the oogonia and oocyte stages. In contrast, germ cells in the male differentiate into mature sperm after the spermatogonia and spermatocyte stages, depending on the sex determination mechanism.

Figure 1. PGC specification and migration. Schematic representation of PGC specification and migration during zebrafish embryonic development. The drawing depicts the distribution of *ddx4* RNA in two positions at the 2-cell stage and later in four positions at the 4- and 8-cell stages. These four clumps segregate into four cells (now PGCs) during the 1k-cell stage. At the 4k-cell stage, the PGCs undergo mitosis and divide. The clusters then migrate during the somitogenesis until they reach the gonadal somatic precursors, which is achieved over the course of 24 hours post-fertilization. Green circles represent the PGCs at different developmental stages. This image is modified from (Yoon et al., 1997; Raz, 2003). This figure is created using Biorender.com.

The sex determination (SD) system determines an organism's sexual fate and initiates gonad differentiation. The SD in teleost is complex and may be influenced by multiple factors such as temperature, pollutants, pH, and other environmental cues, irrespective of their genetic makeup (Devlin and Nagahama, 2002). In zebrafish, the SD is polygenic, where multiple alleles are at play rather than controlled by a single pair of sex chromosomes (Liew et al., 2012; Liew and Orbán, 2014). All juvenile zebrafish first possess an undifferentiated ovary-like gonadal structure in the beginning, regardless of their genotypic sex, which undergoes sex-reversal in male individuals after 20 days post-hatching and transforms into testis, a phenomenon known as hermaphroditism in fish (Yamamoto, 1969). All ovarian gonadal cells undergo programmed cell death in males, and the testicular differentiation resumes (Uchida et al., 2002).

The gonial cells

This part of the discussion deals with the germ cell development and the path PGCs cover after colonizing the undifferentiated gonad, called gonocytes. The gonocytes differentiate into spermatogonia and oogonia depending on the phenotypical sex of the organism. PGCs and the gonial cells are biopotential before the onset of meiosis. Spermatogenesis is an orderly process where diploid spermatogonia proliferate and differentiate to generate millions of mature and flagellated haploid spermatozoa. Spermatogenesis is a continuous process where undifferentiated spermatogonia self-renew to maintain the balance between stem cells and differentiated spermatogonia in order to continue spermatozoa production throughout life. This process is completed in three different phases: 1) spermatogonial or mitotic phase, where type A undifferentiated spermatogonia (A_{und}) gives rise to Type A differentiated spermatogonia (A_{diff}) with reduced potential for self-renewal, Type A spermatogonia differentiates and generated Type B spermatogonia. Type B spermatogonia has several generations based on their morphological aspects, which vary between species (Schulz et al., 2010). 2) Type B spermatogonia undergoes first meiotic division to produce primary spermatocytes, followed by second meiotic division to produce secondary spermatocytes, and 3) the spermiogenic phase, where the spermatids undergo differentiation to produce a large number of haploid and motile spermatozoa (Schulz et al., 2010). Unlike spermatogenesis, oogenesis produces a limited number of mature eggs upon spawning. PGCs transform into oogonia, followed by meiotic division to produce primary oocytes. Primary oocytes undergo vitellogenesis to accumulate nutrition and maternal RNA essential for early embryo development. Finally, ovulation takes place after the maturation of the secondary oocyte (Lubzens et al., 2010).

1.2. Germ cell-based biotechnologies

Germ cell biology received enormous attention with the development of germ cell-specific markers that opened several windows to study germ cell development, visualization, and migration. New-age technologies have developed approaches to isolate, culture, and genetically manipulate germ cells in order to produce transgenic animals. Germ cell markers have contributed to producing gametes through germline chimeras with germ cell transplantation into xenogenic and allogenic recipients; the approach is also known as surrogate production. Surrogate production involves a systematic procedure: 1) harvesting donor germ stem cells (GSCs), 2) endogenous germ cell depletion of the recipient, also known as sterilization of the host, and 3) transplantation of donor GSCs into the recipient. Selecting a suitable GSC type and a transplantation method with higher efficiency is a prerequisite for surrogate production. This author aims to discuss all the methods associated with germ cell transplantation and their limitations and complexity, which may provide new insight for future studies. Genetic improvements through biotechnologies and elucidating the questions associated with these manipulating techniques are the sole purpose of this thesis.

1.2.1. PGC transplantation

PGC manipulation received prominence with the identification *ddx4* homolog gene that encodes an ATP-dependent RNA helicase of the DEAD box family and is expressed exclusively in germ cell lineage, which enables the visualization of PGCs during their migration to the genital ridge using green fluorescent protein (GFP) reporter driven by the cis-regulatory elements of *ddx4* gene that leads to GFP-specific gene expression in the germ cells (Yoshizaki et al., 2002; Kobayashi et al., 2004). Following the identification of the *ddx4* gene, other germ cell-specific markers such as *nanos1* (*nos1*) in zebrafish (Köprunner et al., 2001) and *oryzias latipes ddx4* homolog (*olvas*) in medaka (Kurokawa et al., 2006), were used in teleost to localize PGCs and found to be conserved among species (Maegawa et al., 2002). First PGC transplantation in rainbow trout, where PGCs were isolated from the genital ridges of the hatched larvae and transplanted into the peritoneal cavity of the recipient larvae; subsequently, the transplanted PGCs incorporated into the recipient gonadal somatic cells and differentiated to generate donor-derived gametes (Takeuchi et al., 2003). Following these achievements, Saito et al. demonstrated a precise developmental stage for PGC transplantation between divergent teleost species, where isolated single PGC from the 10–15 somite embryo showed promising results for germline chimera production when transplanted into the marginal region of the blastulae stage embryo (Saito et al., 2008, 2010). They also reported that PGCs isolated from the later developmental stages lost their migration abilities. PGCs retrieved from the 24-hour cultured blastomere retained the potential to differentiate into functional gametes in germline chimera (Kawakami et al., 2010).

Combining PGC cryopreservation with transplantation could be a potential way to preserve the genetic resource of valuable transgenic lines produced to use as models for developmental and other genetic studies. Notably, zebrafish develop into a phenotypical all-male mono-sex population after germ cell depletion and require an absolute number of PGCs to stabilize the ovarian fate (Tzung et al., 2015). In that case, a high number of PGC transplants into the sterile embryo could produce fertile female germline chimera in zebrafish (Zhang et al., 2020). However, this strategy is labor-extensive and skill-sensitive. The present thesis addresses this question by using a genetically compatible larger species in Chapter 2 with gonial cell transplantation. PGC could be the ideal candidate for genome editing to induce desirable traits post-transplantation (Van De Lavoie et al., 2006; Xiong et al., 2013). However, one must focus on the complexity associated with PGC transplantation. Although the incorporation efficiency may be higher with PGCs as they are totipotent and committed to the germ cell lineage fate, the micromanipulation skills required to isolate the single PGCs and their precise transplantation into the recipient seem complicated and not very straightforward. It looks rather theoretical to generate a handful of germline chimera with single PGC transplantation, considering the limited number of PGCs that could be isolated from a single donor individual (Takeuchi et al., 2004). Recently, Wang et al. reported a novel approach to induce a higher number of presumptive PGCs from the zebrafish blastoderm cells using a mRNA cocktail of 9 germplasm factors related to PGC specification and migration, where PGCs from one donor embryo enabled transplantation into 30 recipients (Wang et al., 2023). However, whether this approach is efficiently applicable to other species remains to be seen. Survival of the transplanted embryos is another obstacle that needs special attention in PGC transplantation. Furthermore, isolating PGCs from the donor embryo requires transient or permanent labeling of germ cells. In some species, the generation of the transgenic line is challenging, and temporary germ cell labeling is often performed by microinjection of synthesized mRNA containing GFP reporter regulated by *ddx4* or *nanos1* promoter region into the one-cell stage embryo (Saito

et al., 2008). However, transient labeling doesn't guarantee the labelling of all the PGCs in the embryo, and the effect is not long-lasting. Moreover, microinjection is challenging for some marine species where breeding is implausible in captivity. Harvesting a higher number of PGCs is also a difficult task since PGC culture and induction are not optimized for all species. Considering these limitations, gonial cell transplantation may be feasible for many species in surrogate production, which is discussed in the next section.

Figure 2. An overview of PGC transplantation. The schematic diagram for the PGC transplantation using the blastomere from a 1k-cell stage embryo that can be cultured to induce PGC production followed by long-term preservation using cryopreservation technique and transplanted upon requirement into the 1k-cell stage embryo (a). PGCs harvested from 10–15 somite stage embryos can be transplanted into the blastulae stage embryo and can also be cultured for cell expansion and cryopreserved for long-term storage (b). PGCs that have already migrated into the genital anlagen can be harvested and used for cryopreservation, culture, and transplantation into the same-stage embryo (c). This figure is created using Biorender.com.

Figure 3. GGC transplantation in zebrafish. PGCs from the *vasa::EGFP* transgenic zebrafish were transplanted into the AB wildtype sterile embryos at the mid-blastula stage. The yellow arrow indicates the transplanted donor PGCs and their migration at developmental stages until the Prim-6 stage. This transplantation was performed as a practice during this dissertation.

1.2.2. Gonial cell transplantation

As discussed in section 1.1, gonial cells (spermatogonia/ oogonia) are found in sexually differentiated individuals. In this section, the author provides the advantages of selecting gonial cells over embryonic stem cells and discusses the transplantability success with spermatogonia and oogonia transplantation. Gonial cells are often preferred in germ cell transplantation because of their abundance and ease of isolation from the adult gonad. Hundreds and thousands of gonial cells can be isolated from the adult testis and ovary by enzymatic dissociation. Although these germ cells are already in the differentiated states, they still possess sexual plasticity and can transdifferentiate into both spermatozoa and oocytes in the recipient gonad (Okutsu et al., 2006). Isolation and enrichment of the spermatogonial cells are described in detail in Chapters 2, 3, and 4. Gonial cells are transplanted into the peritoneal cavity of the recipient hatched larvae, and, interestingly, they migrate and are incorporated into the sexually undifferentiated gonad of the recipient. This mechanism is well known in PGCs as they possess pseudopodia that help them migrate towards the gonad guided by chemoattractant (Raz, 2004), but it remains to be unfolded in gonial cells. Spermatogonial cells are the most commonly used gonial cells for transplantation rather than oogonia. The proportion of spermatogonia is higher in adult testis than the proportion of oogonia in the ovary (Ichida et al., 2019), which may substantially affect the transplantation efficiency. The success of transplantation highly depends on the stemness of the transplanted gonial cells. Among the testicular cell suspension, Type A spermatogonia (SPG-A) is reported to bear stemness that can proliferate to recolonize the recipient gonad (Ichida et al., 2019). Therefore, enriching the cell suspension with the SPG-A population may enhance the transplantation efficiency. The efficiency is also reported to be lower in the case of xenotransplantation (Kise et al., 2012), where genetic compatibility between the donor and recipient comes into play, and the gonadal somatic cells of the recipient fail to coalesce with the donor germ cells. However, many other xenogenic transplantations reportedly produced donor-derived gametes (Yamaha et al., 2003; Morita et al., 2015; Silva et al., 2016; Hattori et al., 2019; Franěk et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021), including the study this thesis addressed in Chapter

2 between the species from different genera showed germ cell compatibility. The proliferation and differentiation of the transplant gonial cells are assumed to be guided by the recipient's gonadal somatic cells and the endogenous sex steroids and growth factors. The recipient's gonadal microenvironment thereby controls the differentiation fate followed by the donor's gonial cells (Yoshizaki et al., 2010).

Notably, spermatogonial cell transplantation into the peritoneal cavity requires less intensive micromanipulation techniques than PGC transplantation. The abundance of spermatogonial cells also offers long-term preservation of genetic resources through cryopreservation and restoration with germ cell transplantation (Lee et al., 2013; Pšenička et al., 2016; Franěk et al., 2019a; Morita et al., 2021). *In vitro* expansion of spermatogonial cells with appropriate culture medium, feeder cells, and growth factors is an effective method for species with small gonads that have less number of GSCs, and the cultured cells can be transplanted into hundreds of recipients (Iwasaki-Takahashi et al., 2020). Gonial cell transplantation can also be transplanted into the sterile adult recipient through their genital pore (Lacerda et al., 2010; Ren et al., 2021). It is a less popular method with low transplantation efficiency compared to the peritoneal cavity transplantation into larvae. A possible reason is the developed immunosystem of the adult recipient and the innate immunity of the developed testis, which is more likely to reject the donor germ cells. Hence, peritoneal cavity transplantation is the most commonly used method for gonial cell transplantation. PGC cryopreservation and *in vitro* culture are challenging compared to the gonial cells and require germ cell labeling at the early stage of embryonic development for successful isolation. In contrast, gonial cells can be isolated without labeling and enriched using density gradient centrifugation (Panda et al., 2011). Considering the above characteristics and the reports, gonial cells are comparatively easier to handle and manipulate than PGCs.

Figure 4. An overview of gonial cell transplantation. This figure is created using Biorender.com.

1.2.3. Germ cell depletion techniques

Germ cell depletion is a prerequisite for surrogate production. Induced sterilization of the host is performed at different developmental stages, depending on the techniques, to ensure the complete removal of the endogenous germ cells before introducing the donor germ cells into their gonad. The germ cell-free gonad of the recipient supports colonization of the transplanted donor germ cells and thereby produces gametes from the donor origin. Besides the genetic compatibility and the translatability of donor germ cells, host sterility is another crucial factor that contributes to germline chimera production efficiency. Various methods have been developed recently and optimized for well-known species like zebrafish, medaka, rainbow trout, and sturgeons. In this section, the author discusses different sterilization methods and outlines their limitations.

Gene knockdown and knockout

Silencing the genes essential for germ cell formation and survival at the early developmental stages (one/two-cell stage embryo) can efficiently induce sterility in the recipient. The most commonly used technique for gene knockdown is morpholino antisense oligonucleotide (MO), designed to target the pre-mature or mature mRNA of the gene of interest to prevent mRNA splicing and translation, respectively. In contrast, gene knockout uses the genome editing tool, for example, the CRISPR-Cas9 system or TALEN, to prevent transcription of the target gene by modifying the target gene sequence (Wargelius et al., 2016; Baloch et al., 2019). Both techniques require microinjection at the early stage of embryogenesis before the gonad formation. However, these techniques are useful when the species genome information is well known. *Dead-end* and *nanos1* are well-known genes targeted in zebrafish and medaka for sterility induction (Ciruna et al., 2002; Saito et al., 2010; Li et al., 2016). Gene knockdown by MO targeting *dnd1* mRNA is also utilized in this thesis, and the method is explained in detail in Chapters 2 and 3. Designing MO for translation inhibition and the target sequence for gene modification demands the precise and unique sequence of the target gene, failing which may lead to off-target effect and aberrant phenotype development in the recipient. While germ cell depletion is highly efficient and reliable using these strategies (Franěk et al., 2022), the short window for injection into one to two-cell stage embryos and their survival rate post-injection poses a challenge for large-scale sterile recipient production. In addition, availing nucleotide sequence information for some unknown species and embryos that are not amenable to genetic manipulation could utilize other methods described below for sterility induction.

Chromosomal manipulation

Production of triploid by second polar body retention may induce sterility in some species. This method needs optimization for every species. Triploidy induction refers to the production of individuals with three sets of homologous chromosomes and can be induced in fish by inhibiting the second meiotic division followed by the extrusion of the second polar body (Oliveira et al., 1995; Cuñado et al., 2002). Triploid induction is achieved by heat, cold shock, or hydrostatic pressure immediately after fertilization. The duration and the mode of shock vary between species. Triploids usually have underdeveloped gonads lacking post-meiotic germ cells (Franěk et al., 2019b). Some triploid species produce a small amount of spermatozoa that are aneuploid and abnormal (Takeuchi et al., 2018). This strategy is useful for the species that are difficult for genetic manipulation or microinjection. Several hundreds of recipients can be generated for large-scale germ cell transplantation, but the incorporation of the donor germ cells post-transplantation may be a challenge because the presence of endogenous germ cells may outcompete donor germ cells, thereby reducing the incorporation efficiency.

Hybridization

Interspecies hybridization between two closely related species sometimes produces sterile offspring that can be used for surrogate production. Cross-breeding between two different species affects sterility in several ways. Some hybrids possess well-developed gonads mostly occupied with oogonia or spermatogonia (Hamaguchi and Sakaizumi, 1992), reported to be caused by aberrant homologous recombination during meiosis, and some hybrids contain gonads that are underdeveloped and thread-like structures with no germ cells. It is reported to be caused by the mitotic arrest of PGC (Yoshikawa et al., 2018). However, not all cross-breed individuals are sterile. Hybrids produced by *in vitro* fertilization of female zebrafish and male pearl danio are reportedly sterile, and the same protocol has been applied in Chapter 3 of this thesis to produce recipients for surrogate production (Wong et al., 2011). In addition, interspecific hybrids between other species have been successfully used for germ cell transplantation (Kawamura et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2020). The drawback of these methods is the transplantation efficiency due to the presence of meiotic arrested germ cells that can significantly affect the growth and proliferation of donor germ cells and reduce the production of functional donor-derived gametes, which is thoroughly discussed in Chapter 3 using high-throughput whole genome bisulfite sequencing.

Chemical and radiation treatment

UV radiation is reported for sterility induction in the endangered sturgeon species. Sturgeon embryos are sensitive to micromanipulation and MO treatment, hence resulting in high mortality post-injection. UV irradiation of the vegetal pole of the sturgeon embryo, where the germplasm is located, is shown to induce sterility (Saito et al., 2018).

Sterilization by chemical treatment is the least popular method in fish and is performed in sexually competent adult fish. The most common method is the injection of a cytostatic drug, busulfan, directly into the genital papilla of adults with a combination of high temperatures at an optimum dose (Majhi et al., 2009; Nóbrega et al., 2010; Lacerda et al., 2010). Busulfan interferes with cell proliferation and causes endogenous germ cell degeneration. However, this method fails to remove all the germ cells, and a high dosage of busulfan is toxic to the cells. In addition, this treatment is only possible in sexually competent fish and is not promising for xenogenic transplantation (Goto and Saito, 2019). Allogenic transplantation, where the immune rejection of donor germ cells is less likely, may use busulfan to produce a large number of recipients.

1.3. Epigenetic changes associated with germ-cell-based biotechnologies

Epigenetics refers to processes that result in heritable alterations in gene activity without manipulating the underlying DNA sequence (Jablonka and Lamb, 2002). Handling the donor germ cell during enzymatic or mechanical cell isolation from the intact tissue and their proliferation in the host gonad post-transplantation may disturb the original epigenetic makeup of the donor germline. Epigenetics is the well-known regulator of gene expression through DNA methylation, histone modification, and non-coding RNAs. Surrogate production technologies involve many systematic procedures that may lead to the remodelling of the epigenome in the donor germline, a caveat of germ cell transplantation that questions its practical reliability. The perturbed epigenome may induce phenotypical anomalies that can be potentially inherited by future generations produced via surrogates, also known as intergenerational for the transient or transgenerational inheritance for prolonged maintenance of inherited epigenetic marks. Epigenetics modifications remain to be unfolded in donor-derived gametes produced by surrogate broodstocks. In fish, epigenetics reprogramming

is best studied in zebrafish (Jiang et al., 2013; Potok et al., 2013; Skvortsova et al., 2019) and medaka (*Oryzias latipes*) (Wang and Bhandari, 2020) during embryonic development. In medaka, PGCs undergo DNA methylation and histone marks reprogramming like mice and humans, and almost all epigenetic marks are discarded (Wang and Bhandari, 2020). On the contrary, the zebrafish germline lacks epigenetic reprogramming post-fertilization and preserves paternal epigenetic marks from 4–36 h post-fertilization (Skvortsova et al., 2019). However, the information on later developmental stages is still unknown. Considering these current findings, it is thoughtworthy to consider evaluating the environmental or chemical stressors that induce epigenetic changes in the germline during the window of germ cell isolation, proliferation, and differentiation in the host gonad using zebrafish as a model. In addition to GCT, it is also crucial to know how different surrogates are treated with varying methods of sterilization, how their phylogenetic distance/the degree of genetic compatibility can influence the epigenome, and to what extent.

The aims of the thesis

The presented thesis aimed to explore the compatibility between foreign germline cells and gonadal somatic cells of species from different genera to produce germline chimera with enhanced features, focusing mainly on fecundity with a new species, giant danio (*Devario aequipinnatus*). The effort is made to understand the deeper level of genetic information changes associated with the surrogate production technique resulting from the recipient gonadal microenvironment interaction with the donor germ cell using two well-known freshwater species, zebrafish and pearl danio, which may provide a new perspective on surrogate production and its application in aquaculture.

The specific objectives of the thesis were the following:

1. Optimization of germ cell transplantation technique to produce a big-body sized surrogate for zebrafish with comparatively higher fecundity and assessing the sexual phenotype of sterile giant danio recipient in order to check the possibility of producing zebrafish donor-derived oocyte.
2. A thorough exploration of the epigenetic perturbation and their intergenerational inheritance effect caused by germ cell manipulation and their development in the foreign environment of the recipient gonad in both intra- and interspecific surrogates with single base-resolution whole genome bisulfite sequencing.
3. Development of a unique method to harvest viable germ cells from the donor for transplantation without comprising their survival and reproductive output using two small species, zebrafish and killifish (*Nothobranchius furzeri*).

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CHAPTER 2

ENHANCEMENT OF ZEBRAFISH SPERM PRODUCTION VIA A LARGE BODY-SIZED SURROGATE WITH GERM CELL TRANSPLANTATION

Nayak, R., Franěk, R., Šindelka, R., Pšenička, M., 2023. Enhancement of zebrafish sperm production via a large body-sized surrogate with germ cell transplantation. *Commun. Biol.* 6, 412.

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My share of this work is about 70% (manuscript writing, experimental work, and data analyses).

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Enhancement of zebrafish sperm production via a large body-sized surrogate with germ cell transplantation

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Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) is a commonly-used vertebrate model species for many research areas. However, its low milt volume limits effective cryopreservation of sperm from a single individual and often precludes dividing a single semen sample to conduct multiple downstream procedures such as genomic DNA/RNA extraction and in-vitro fertilization. Here, we apply germ stem cell transplantation to increase zebrafish sperm production in a closely related larger species from the same subfamily, giant danio *Devario aequipinnatus*. The endogenous germ cell of the host is depleted by dead-end morpholino antisense oligonucleotide. Histology of the sterile gonad and quantitative PCR of gonadal tissue reveals all sterile giant danio develop the male phenotype. Spermatogonial cells of Tg(*ddx4:egfp*) transgenic zebrafish are transplanted into sterile giant danio larvae, and 22% of recipients (germline chimera) produce donor-derived sperm at sexual maturation. The germline chimera produce approximately three-fold the volume of sperm and 10-fold the spermatozoon concentration of the donor. The donor-derived sperm is functional and gives rise to viable progeny upon fertilization of donor oocytes. We show that the issue of low milt volume can be effectively addressed by employing a larger surrogate parent.

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Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) is a popular model species used to study developmental biology, genetics, drug development, and many other research areas^{1,2} because of their remarkable characteristics such as small size, easy breeding, external fertilization, transparent embryos with rapid development^{3,4}. However, having many advantageous characteristics, zebrafish males produce only 1 µl of milt because of their small body size⁵. This can be a drawback for research requiring cryopreservation of sperm for genetic resource conservation of valuable zebrafish mutant strains and transgenic lines⁶, particularly when maintaining the individual genotype precludes pooling sperm of several males. The motility and fertilization rate of thawed spermatozoa from such a small volume of semen may be extremely low, hampering the recovery of genetic lines^{7–9}. Considering these limitations, we investigated the transplantation of zebrafish spermatogonial cells into one of their closely related species, the giant danio (*Devario aequipinnatus*), to assess its suitability as a surrogate parent for zebrafish. Giant danio belongs to the family *Cyprinidae* and is considered a phylogenetically closely related species to zebrafish¹⁰. Giant danio reaches 7–8 cm in captivity. It exhibits characteristics functionally similar to zebrafish. External fertilization and transparent eggs make it amenable to genetic manipulation, imaging, and visual observation. Notably, the fecundity of giant danio is greater than that of zebrafish. This species could potentially be a suitable surrogate for zebrafish to boost gamete production.

Surrogate broodstock production plays an important role in increasing aquaculture productivity¹¹. The protocol requires transplantation of germline stem cells (GSC) from the donor of interest into a sterile host in order to produce donor-derived gametes. Success depends on factors such as (1) the evolutionary distance between the donor and recipient¹², (2) ablation of the host endogenous germ cell to prevent recipient-derived gamete production¹³, and (3) a suitable developmental stage of the recipient^{14,15}. The first attempt to produce germline chimeras in a fish was in zebrafish with the aim of determining if embryonic cells from the donor contributed to the host germline¹⁶. Germline stem cell transplant of a large-bodied species into a small fish with a shorter generation time has enabled rapid domestication of marine species, including Japanese yellowtail *Seriola quinqueradiata* transplanted into jack mackerel *Trachurus japonicus*¹⁷ and commercially valuable tiger puffer *Takifugu rubripes* transplanted into grass puffer *Takifugu niphobolus*¹⁸. Donor-derived viable sperm of landlocked Atlantic salmon *Salmo salar* was obtained with a triploid rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss* surrogate to reduce the generation time and improve environment adaptation¹⁹. Common carp *Cyprinus carpio* gametes were produced through spermatogonial cell transplantation into the peritoneal cavity of goldfish *Carassius auratus*²⁰ to preserve their germplasm in a smaller surrogate. Psenicka et al.²¹ extended a strategy for germ cell cryopreservation of a nearly extinct sturgeon species. Such studies have shown that GSC transplantation tools can be a vital contribution to aquaculture.

Our study was designed to focus on the following key points; (1) to test the hypothesis if giant danio develops into male after endogenous germ cell ablation, (2) to enhance the fecundity of zebrafish using giant danio as a surrogate. Zebrafish is believed to have a polygenic sex determination system where multiple genes throughout the genome are identified as associated with sex determination²². Many studies have shown that zebrafish develop male-like characteristics after endogenous germ cell depletion^{23–25}, making it impossible to obtain donor-derived oocytes through sterile zebrafish surrogates by spermatogonial cell transplantation into the larvae. So, this study evaluated whether, being closely related to zebrafish, sterile giant danios recipients will also give rise to monosex male populations. If sterile giant danio recipients do not give rise to monosex male populations, we may be

able to produce zebrafish donor-derived oocytes in giant danio surrogates. Giant danio surrogacy may be of significance considering the need to preserve hundreds of mutant zebrafish strains, which is currently possible only by sperm cryopreservation.

This study shows that giant danio developed the male phenotype after endogenous germ cell depletion. Sterile giant danio larvae transplanted with Tg(*ddx4:egfp*) zebrafish spermatogonial cells produced a significantly higher volume of fertile donor-derived sperm upon sexual maturation than the donor.

Results

Recipient production. According to the study design (Fig. 1), we first spawn giant danio broodstocks to establish sterile recipients. We obtained ~3000 eggs from a single giant danio female and ~6 µl milt from individual males by abdominal pressure for in-vitro fertilization. The survival of MO-treated recipients was 50% of that of the control group (Table 1) and was consistent among all females. After injection, the positive control group injected with *gfpUTRnanos3* and the MO co-injected with *gfpUTRnanos3* group were screened under a fluorescence for GFP expression in the primordial germ cells (PGC). PGCs are the precursors of germ cell lineage that arise at the marginal part of blastodisc at the blastula stage and migrate to the genital anlage during embryogenesis^{26–30}. The positive control showed the presence of primordial germ cells (PGCs) in all injected embryos ($n = 50$) during the segmentation period, whereas the MO co-injected with *gfpUTRnanos3* group exhibited no GFP expression at any developmental stage (Fig. 2a, b'), confirming that the designed MO successfully prevented PGC migration in all injected embryos ($n = 50$) with 100% efficiency. Both male and female controls showed well developed gonads with mature spermatozoa and oocytes (Fig. 2d, e"). The gonads of morphants were challenging to identify after the dissection and degutting. Tissue on both sides of the gas bladder was negligible under the stereo microscope, and only identifiable after Bouin's fixation (Fig. 2c). The morphology of the gonad looked similar to sterile zebrafish testis (Fig. 2c', e")¹³. A similar structure was observed in other morphants, implying that the giant danios are males without germ cells (Supplementary Fig. 1). The RT-qPCR data of gonadal tissue showed expression of *sox9a* (essential for testes development) similar to that of the male controls and lower expression of *cyp19a1a* mRNA (expressed preferentially in female) (Fig. 2f). Sanger's sequencing confirmed the sequence specificity of all genes (Supplementary Note 1). All amplified sequences showed >93% identity to the zebrafish sequence after nucleotide BLAST. *Vasa* expression was negligible in all the morphants with both RT-qPCR and immunohistochemistry (Fig. 2f–i").

Transplant success; germline chimera reproduction. Initially, the donor testicular cells were prepared without density gradient centrifugation, and the transplant efficacy was low. Recipients with GFP-positive cells were scarce after one week ($n = 12$, 12%), and those cells gradually disappeared. No germline chimera was produced. After this, Ficoll was used to enrich the testicular cell suspension and to separate the excess spermatozoa from the larger cells, such as spermatogonia. Transplanted recipients ($n = 100$) were checked immediately after transplant to ensure the presence of Tg(*ddx4:egfp*) spermatogonial cells, and we found GFP-positive cells in all transplanted individuals (Fig. 3a, a'). The surviving recipients ($n = 85$, 85%) were screened one week post-transplant (1wpt) to identify the GFP-positive recipients ($n = 35$, 41.2%), which were observed to have few GFP-positive cells (see Fig. 3b, b'). After one month, a cluster of GFP-positive cells near the gas bladder was observed in five dissected fish (see Fig. 3c–e'). The number was increased from 1wpt, implying that the

Fig. 1 Schematic of study design. GD-giant danio, MO-dead-end antisense morpholino oligonucleotide, L-15-Leibovitz's L-15 Medium. This figure was created with BioRender.com.

Table 1 Survival rate of the recipients of morpholino injection.

	Total embryos	25-somite (%)	Hatched (%)	Day-5 (%)
Morpholino only	257	193 (75.1%)	145 (56.4%)	123 (47.9%)
Control	200	187 (93.5%)	187 (93.5%)	183 (91.5%)

transplanted spermatogonia could incorporate into the giant danio empty gonad and proliferate. Three recipients died during the rearing process. The remaining recipients were stripped for milt collection at five months ($n = 27$). Only six males produced milt. Total sperm count ($1.28 \pm 0.4 \times 10^4$) and the milt volume were low ($\sim 1 \mu\text{l}$) in all males, and the rate of fertilization of the donor egg was $<20\%$.

A single milt-producing recipient was dissected to evaluate gonad development, revealing unilaterally developed testis with strong GFP expression. Histology showed a well-developed structure with all stages of spermatogenesis and the presence of mature spermatozoa (see Fig. 3f–h^{''}), suggesting that the germline chimera is sexually mature at five months post-transplant, which is similar to the giant danio males. After a further month, the remaining 26 recipients were again stripped, with only the five surviving previously spawning males producing milt. GFP-specific PCR showed positive amplification in all five males (Fig. 3j), suggesting that the sperm produced was of donor origin (germline production rate 22%, $n = 6$). There was no GFP amplification in the giant danio control male. The sperm samples were examined under fluorescence microscopy to assess GFP expression, as the sperm from Tg(ddx4:egfp) lines also emits fluorescence because of residual protein near the spermatozoon head region. We observed the GFP signal in all spermatozoa (Fig. 3i, i').

Reproductive characteristics of germline chimera. A significantly higher volume of milt was collected from the five

Table 2 Combinations of fertilization trials between the germline chimeras and the control group.

Combinations	Female	Male
ZFF × GCM	Zebrafish female	Germline chimera male
ZFF × ZFM	Zebrafish female	Zebrafish male
ZFF × GDM	Zebrafish female	Giant danio male
GDF × GDM	Giant danio female	Giant danio male
GDF × GCM	Giant danio female	Germline chimera male

germline chimeras than from the zebrafish males but less than from the giant danio (Fig. 4a–c). A similar pattern was observed in spermatozoon concentration. Fertilization of donor oocytes was unsuccessful at the first spawning, likely due to the low number of spermatozoa. In the second in-vitro trial (Table 2), the rate of fertilization by the germline chimera males was similar to the zebrafish control groups, while the fertilization rate of the giant danio eggs by the germline chimera sperm was negligible ($\sim 5\%$). None survived to the segmentation period (Table 3). Information of the fertilization success of each germline chimera is presented in Supplementary Table 2. All swim-up (day 5) larvae (F1 progeny) produced by the donor-derived sperm were all positive for GFP-specific PCR amplifications, while the progeny from the AB control group showed no amplification. Few larvae from the AB control and germline chimera groups reared until their maturation. At two months post-fertilization, the adult progeny was examined under

Fig. 2 Dead-end knock-down of giant danio. **a, a'** Embryo injected with MO plus *gfp*UTRnanos3 during the segmentation period shows no GFP-positive cells, $n = 50$. **b-b'** PGCs in a positive control injected with *gfp*UTRnanos3 only shows the presence of a cluster of PGCs under fluorescence (yellow arrowhead), $n = 50$. **c** The midsection of a 1-year-old morphant fixed with Bouin's shows a pair of underdeveloped gonads, thread-like structures tightly attached to the dorsal body wall (red arrowhead). **c'** Transverse section of the midsection and bilateral gonads (black arrowheads). **c''** Magnification of the region of the right gonad indicated by black arrowhead shows a testis-like structure with empty lumen lacking germ cells. A total of 10 gonads were analyzed for histology. **d, d'** Control giant danio female with well-developed ovary mostly filled with post-vitellogenin oocyte (blue arrowhead) and few cortical alveoli stages (black arrowhead). **e, e'** Control male with normally developed testis showing spermatozoa (black arrowhead). **f** The graph shows the expression levels of *sox9a*, *cyp19a1a*, and *Vasa (ddx4)* in the gonadal tissue of the morphants ($n = 10$ biological replicates), control males ($n = 3$ biological replicates) and control females ($n = 3$ biological replicates) relative to the expression level of reference gene *efl1a11*. The relative expression is calculated by the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Cq}$ method; data are presented as mean \pm SD. Source data for this graph is provided in Supplementary Table 1. **g, g'** Sections of Vasa-Immunohistochemistry shows well-developed ovary of four-month-old control giant danio expressing prominent signal for Vasa (green) with red arrowheads indicating oocyte at the primary growth stage. **h, h''** transverse section of the control testis and red asterisks indicating the spermatozoa. **i, i'** Tissue sections of the MO-treated recipient (indicated by yellow arrowhead) with no expression of Vasa and signal only for DAPI. Three sterile recipients and three controls were analyzed for Vasa-Immunohistochemistry. Filter used, bright field for **a** and **b** and DA/FI/TRITC for **a'** and **b'**. Scale bars, **a, a', b, b', c', d', e'** = 100 μ m, **c, d, e** = 1 mm, **c', d', e'** = 200 μ m, **g, g', h, h', i** and **i'** = 100 μ m.

fluorescence (Leica Fluorescence Microscope). We observed prominent GFP expression near the putative gonadal region in the progeny derived from the donor-derived sperm but none in the control individuals (Fig. 4d–e'). To confirm that the line of interest can be recovered, we applied a standard breeding protocol to obtain fish with the *Tg(ddx4:egfp)* transgene. The sexually mature F1 progeny were subjected to semi-in-vitro fertilization, and the resulting F2 progeny expressed a strong EGFP signal at different developmental stages (Fig. 4f–i'). The external appearance of the adult donor-derived progeny was similar to that of the zebrafish (Supplementary Figure 3).

Discussion

We produced zebrafish donor-derived sperm with a total spermatozoon count of $67.02 \pm 27.39 \times 10^4$ (Mean \pm SD, $n = 5$) and obtained viable progeny from giant danio surrogates by

spermatogonia transplant into the dead-end knock-down sterile host. In the preliminary experiment with total testicular cell suspension, we observed low survival of the transplanted cells at one week, decreasing to zero in all recipients. Thereafter, the donor testicular cell preparation was subjected to density gradient centrifugation to separate the spermatogonia from other cells (mainly spermatozoa). We used the same number of donors ($n = 4$) as in the previous protocol and observed improved transplant efficacy, suggesting that the excess number of spermatozoa in the cell suspension interferes with the spermatogonial cell incorporation into the giant danio gonad and affects their survival. We achieved 22% ($n = 6$) success with germline chimera production, and the mature individuals produced viable sperm and progeny when crossed with donor oocytes by in-vitro fertilization. The F1 progeny produced by the donor-derived sperm carried the *Tg(ddx4:egfp)* gene, confirmed by GFP-specific PCR of the larvae. The EGFP expression in the F1 progeny was only

Fig. 3 Intra-peritoneal spermatogonium transplant from *Tg(ddx4:egfp)* zebrafish into sterile giant danio recipients. **a–a'** Detection of GFP-positive cells under fluorescence immediately after transplant into the posterior part of the gas bladder ($n = 100$). The magnified area is the red dashed rectangle, and cells are indicated by red arrowheads. **b, b'** The number of transplanted cells decreased seven days post-transplant, possibly because damaged spermatogonia and other cells, such as spermatids, are degraded over time, and few germ cells survive to proliferate. Eighty-five survived recipients were analyzed at 7 dpt. **c, d** Two dissected recipients three weeks post-transplant (3wpt) show few GFP-positive cells in the genital ridge. **e** Another recipient of the same age group shows a cluster of cells indicated by a red dashed rectangle. **e'** A total of five recipients were analyzed at 3wpt. **f** One five-month-old degutted germline chimera shows the presence of unilaterally developed testis under fluorescence microscope (FITC filter), and the red arrowhead indicates the testis. **f'** Higher magnification of the testis. **g** Longitudinal section of the same testis (merged image, the blue color is DAPI, and the green color is for GFP expression). **h** Higher magnification of the region depicted by the white rectangle from image **g**, under the DAPI filter. **h'** The same region under the FITC filter shows the expression of Vasa. **h''** Merge image for DAPI and FITC, and the red arrowheads indicate the spermatozoa populations. Approximately twenty sections were analyzed to check the Vasa expression **i, i'** Sperm from the germline chimera ($n = 5$) under brightfield and the GFP expression of the residual Vasa protein near the midpiece of the spermatozoa (indicated by red arrowheads) under the FITC filter. **j** The gel image of the five germline chimera (GC1–GC5) shows positive amplification for the GFP gene, and the product length is 187 bp loaded on 1.5% agarose gel. GD– sperm from giant danio males shows no PCR amplification, L–100bp DNA marker, and NTC is no template control. Uncropped and unedited gel image for this figure is provided as Supplementary Fig. 2. Filter used DA/FI/TRITC (**a', b', c, d, e, e'**) and brightfield (**a, b**). dpt – day post-transplant, wpt – week post-transplant. Scale bars: **a, b, f**, and **f'** = 1 mm, **b', a', c, d, e, e', h** and **h'** = 100 μ m, **g** = 200 μ m, **i** and **i'** = 10 μ m.

observed in the adults because the *Tg(ddx4:egfp)* transgene is inherited from the male (*Tg(ddx4:egfp)* donor-derived sperm). Its expression was observed in the early developmental stages of the F2 progeny, since the *Tg(ddx4:egfp)* transgene was maternally contributed³¹.

We attempted to boost milt production by giant danio surrogate and obtained higher sperm volume compared to zebrafish but than in the giant danio. The possible reason could be the development of one testis in the germline chimera, evident in post-transplant images. In all examined recipients, GFP-positive cells were observed on only one side of the coelomic cavity. A similar phenomenon of unilateral testis development was observed in the zebrafish after testicular cell transplant^{13,32}. Nevertheless, the germline chimeras in this study produced more milt than did the donor. The spermatozoon concentration of the germline chimeras was higher than in the zebrafish, and the in-vitro fertilization rate was similar to that of the donor group. Giant danio males are reported to reach sexual maturation at five months and the zebrafish at ~3 months^{33,34}. Our study showed that the germline chimera matured at five months, as evidenced by histology. However, the amount of milt was less, with a lower number of spermatozoa. Successful spawning was only obtained at six months, suggesting that the transplanted donor cells exhibit slower gonad maturation compared to giant danio males, delaying the onset of spermiation in the germline chimeras. This observation is not new, as few previous studies have reported zebrafish to become sexually mature ~6 months after germ cell transplantation^{35,36}. We cannot completely exclude low germline

chimera production efficacy in this study. A possible reason for this could be the low abundance of Type A spermatogonia (SPG-A) in the transplanted cells. Previous studies have shown that only undifferentiated germ cells such as SPG-A have the potential to be incorporated into the host gonad^{37,38}. Although we performed density gradient centrifugation for the spermatogonial isolation, it still could not ensure a higher proportion of SPG-A in the cell suspension. The enrichment of the SPG-A population by cell sorting may enhance the colonization efficiency in xenogenic transplantation³⁹.

Our study showed that giant danios develop as male after endogenous germ cell depletion. We randomly screened 10 dnd-MO-treated individuals and found a testis-like structure along with higher *sox9a* mRNA expression in the gonadal tissue and no *cyp19a1a* expression. Gonad-specific aromatase *cyp19a1a* is primarily involved in estrogen production⁴⁰, and estrogen stimulates ovarian development in fish⁴¹. The downregulation of *cyp19a1a* has been reported to promote masculinization⁴². On the contrary, *sox9a* is required for testis determination^{43,44}. Moreover, no female germline chimera was found after transplantation, indicating that giant danio may require a certain number of PGCs to achieve the female fate, as is the case with medaka (*Oryzias latipes*) and zebrafish^{23,25,45,46}. Xenogenic germ cell transplantation from other species to zebrafish host was performed^{47,48} or between the different zebrafish strains^{13,32}. We successfully established a zebrafish surrogate parent that can produce more sperm than the zebrafish. A significant increase in sperm volume and concentration in giant danio surrogates explains

the relationship between body mass and reproductive output. Reportedly, reproduction output increases isometrically with body weight and size⁴⁹. Gamete biomass scaled sub-linearly with body size in several species, including fish⁵⁰. Giant danio is three times larger than zebrafish in size, which justifies the production of more milt volume in giant danio surrogates.

This represents the first report of zebrafish germ cell transplant into a host of a different genus. Although there are advanced methods developed for zebrafish sperm cryopreservation involving pooling the semen from many individuals⁵ digestion of whole testes⁵, it is challenging to cryopreserve the small volume of semen produced by an individual male⁸. Milt volume varies

Fig. 4 Milt production of germline chimera and germline transmission in progeny from donor-derived sperm. **a** Spermatozoon concentration expressed in ($10^4 \mu\text{l}^{-1}$), $n = 5$ biological replicates, **b** The total volume of milt obtained from three groups, $n = 5$ biological replicates, and **c** the total spermatozoon number, $n = 5$ biological replicates. Data are represented as mean \pm SD. ZF, zebrafish males, GD, giant danio males and GCM, germline chimera males. $p < 0.0001$ (****), $p < 0.002$ (**), and $p < 0.0332$ (*). See Supplementary Table 3 for milt production of each germline chimera. **d** Two-month-old F1 progeny produced by donor-derived sperm and AB female oocyte under brightfield. The gonad region is delineated by the yellow border. **d'** The same fish under the FITC filter shows the expression of GFP in the designated area. **e** Control progeny under bright field. **e'** Specimen showing no GFP expression under the FITC filter, both progeny were derived from oocytes of the same AB female. **f, f'** Embryo from the adult F1 progeny with strong GFP expression in the blastomere. **g, g'** F2 progeny at 20-somite stage showing GFP expression in PGCs, indicated by a yellow arrowhead. **h-h'** same embryo on day-5, and PGCs are indicated by a yellow arrowhead near the gas bladder. **i, i'** Eight days old larvae. Scale bars, **d, d'**, **e, e'** = 1 mm, and **f-f'** = 100 μm .

Table 3 Fertilization success with donor-derived sperm. Data represent mean \pm SD, $n = 5$ biological replicates; (-) indicates no survival in the group.

Group ($n = 5$)	Total eggs	256-cell stage (%)	25-somite (%)	Day 5 (%)
ZFF \times GCM	100	81.1 \pm 4.5	76.7 \pm 7.5	76.7 \pm 7.4
ZFF \times ZFM	100	84.7 \pm 3.4	77.1 \pm 5.4	75.7 \pm 7.2
ZFF \times GDM	100	4.6 \pm 3.9	—	—
GDF \times GDM	100	90.3 \pm 5.7	87.5 \pm 4.3	87.3 \pm 4.6
GDF \times GCM	100	4.8 \pm 4.4	—	—

among zebrafish individuals, with some producing $< 1 \mu\text{l}$. In our study, the germline chimeras produced sperm of ~ 10 fold the spermatozoon concentration of that of zebrafish, with maximum milt volume ranging from 3.2 μl to 4 μl (Supplementary Table 3). This may provide the potential to perform several downstream processes simultaneously from one individual. Many transgenic and other mutant zebrafish strains have been developed to study genetics, drug development, and other areas of human disease^{51,52}, and maintaining those valuable stocks cannot only be possible through sperm cryopreservation. Another method is required to overcome this issue. The germplasm of any zebrafish line can be transplanted into the giant danio and resurrected with more gametes since both giant danio and zebrafish take a similar period after transplantation to achieve sexual maturation. Giant danio culture and maintenance does not differ from that of zebrafish. Their feeding and breeding behavior are identical, and, like zebrafish, giant danio can reproduce multiple times per month. Sperm cryopreservation is not the only way to preserve the germplasm, and the confirmation of giant danio as a suitable surrogate parent for zebrafish means that studies may assess the potential for transplanting germ cells from a cryopreserved gonad into the giant danio recipients. Transplanted cryopreserved testes have been reported to colonize the zebrafish gonad and produce viable sperm⁵³. A similar approach can possibly be applied to giant danio. There are many reports of germline chimera production via transplanting cells of larger species into small-bodied species in order to shorten the reproductive cycle^{17,20}. Our study reports surrogate production techniques that can be helpful in increasing gamete production by xenogenic spermatogonial transplantation from smaller species into a larger recipient. Although there is existing literature reporting goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) gamete increment via common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) surrogates, where common carp recipients were treated with busulfan (myleran) for endogenous germ cell ablation⁵⁴. However, we cannot exclude the fact that busulfan cannot ensure the complete depletion of all the germ cells in the gonad and may give rise to recipient-derived gametes¹¹. Higher dosage of busulfan also causes cytotoxicity and increase mortality in the treated individuals⁵⁵. Dead-end gene knockdown by antisense morpholino oligonucleotide which is applied in our study for recipient production has been reported to be more

effective than any other method for germ cell depletion for surrogate production in fish¹³.

In summary, our study established a surrogate parent for zebrafish from a different genus with highly concentrated donor-derived sperm and a fertilization rate comparable to that of the donor individuals. Giant danio germline chimeras may provide a solution to the limitations encountered with low-sperm production by zebrafish individuals and potentially be used to preserve the transgenic and mutant zebrafish lines produced to use for various research purposes.

Methods

Fish husbandry. Giant danio broodstock were maintained in the Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters (FFPW), the University of South Bohemia in Ceske Budejovice, Vodňany. Rearing temperature was $25 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and photoperiod 14 L:10D. Fish were fed commercial dry flakes twice, and blood worms once, daily. Zebrafish lines were obtained from the University of Liege, Belgium⁵⁶, held in our facility for several generations at 28°C , photoperiod 14L:10D, and fed *Artemia nauplii* and dry diet. All the experiments were conducted at the facility of FFPW.

Dead-end (*dnd*) gene amplification and morpholino designing. Total RNA was extracted from the gonads of three-month-old giant danio using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen). Extracted RNA was processed for cDNA synthesis using WizScript™ RT FDMix, thermal cycler programmed at 25°C for 10 min, 42°C for 30 min, 85°C for 5 min, and held at 4°C . The *dnd* gene was amplified from the cDNA using 0.5 μl of forward primer 5'-TCCACCAATTTACAGGTGTGTC-3' and reverse primer 5'-CGAGGCTGTAAGAGGGTACAC-3' and 5 μl of PPP master mix (Top Bio). The primers for the *dnd* gene were designed from the available zebrafish *dnd1* mRNA sequence (accession number NM_212795.1). The amplification conditions were 94°C for 5 min and 35 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, 58°C for 30 s, and 72°C for 45 s with a final extension of 72°C for 5 min. The amplified product was checked for positive amplification on 2% agarose gel (Supplementary Fig. 4). The amplicon was cut with a sterile scalpel from the gel and purified using the GeneAll ExpinTM Combo GP kit, followed by Sanger's sequencing. Three individuals of each sex were sequenced to confirm the sequence specificity. The *dnd*-morpholino (MO) was designed according to the start codon of the cDNA sequence (Supplementary Note 1 shows the sequence of the *dnd* amplicon). The resulting *dnd* sequence was compared with available *dnd* sequences (data obtained from the NCBI database) from other species including zebrafish (Accession number NM_212795.1), medaka (NM_001164516.1), goldfish (JN578697.1), common carp (MN447719.1), and rainbow trout (NM_001124661.1) to identify conserved nucleotides across species (Supplementary Fig. 5). The designed MO sequence for giant danio is 5'-CTGTAATGCCGTTGAGCCTCATG-3'.

Sterile recipient production. Giant danio broodstock were held in breeding chambers (6.8" L \times 4" W \times 3.9" H) at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Males and females were separated by a barrier in the afternoon prior to spawning. The following day, barriers were removed, allowing mating, and fish were observed for oviposition. Gametes were collected from breeding pairs: Semen from the males was collected in E400 extender (immobilization solution at 1:10 dilution) by gentle abdominal massage. Eggs collected from the ovulating females into a clean Petri dish, by gentle abdominal pressure, were promptly fertilized in vitro. Post-fertilization embryos were divided into four groups: (1) MO only ($n = 257$), (2) MO co-injected with gfpUTRnanos3 (to confirm the depletion of PGC, $n = 50$)⁵⁶, (3) gfpUTRnanos3 only (positive control to confirm that PGCs are labeled, $n = 50$), and (4) intact control ($n = 200$). 1 mM stock MO was diluted to 0.1 mM with nuclease-free water (Ambion™, ThermoFisherScientific) and 2 M potassium chloride to a final concentration 0.2 M. Embryos were injected through the chorion at the 1–2 cell stage into the yolk near the blastodisc using a stereomicroscope using a glass capillary (World Precision Instruments, Item No. IB100-4) connected to a micro-manipulator (M-152, Narishige, Japan) and FemtoJet 4x microinjector (Eppendorf, Germany). All experimental groups were cultured at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with a daily change

of fresh temperate water. The survival rate of MO-treated embryos and intact controls were recorded until the day 5.

Transplantation. Three-month-old Tg(*ddx4:egfp*) male zebrafish ($n = 4$) were killed with overdose of anesthetic tricaine methane sulfonate (MS222). Testes were aseptically removed, placed in 1× phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and cut with sterile scissors into small fragments then washed twice to remove excess sperm. The tissue fragments were transferred into the cell dissociation solution containing PBS with 0.1% trypsin, 0.05% collagenase (Gibco), and 30 µg/ml of DNase. The tissue was further minced with scissors and incubated for 50 min at 22–23 °C on a rocking shaker. The cell suspension was then mixed with L-15 (Leibovitz medium) cell culture medium supplemented with 10% (final concentration) fetal bovine serum (FBS) at a 1:1 ratio and filtered through a 30 µm pore (CellTrics) to remove debris. The cell suspension was subjected to density gradient centrifugation using Ficoll-Paque™ PLUS (GE Healthcare) at 600 × g for 20 min. After centrifugation, two upper layers containing early-stage spermatogonia were carefully transferred to a new sterile tube according to Panda et al.⁵⁷. The collected cells were washed with 1× PBS to remove ficoll at the same speed, and the cell pellet was resuspended with the 30 µl of L-15 medium with 10% FBS. Seven-day-old germ cell-depleted recipients were anesthetized with 0.08% MS222 and placed on the Petri plate coated with 1% agar. The spermatogonia cell suspension was loaded into the pulled glass capillary connected to the injector as described above for morpholino injection. Approximately 500–600 cells were transplanted into the posterior part of the gas bladder in the recipients ($n = 100$).

Germline chimera reproduction and donor-derived gamete confirmation. One-week post-transplant (1wpt), recipients ($n = 100$) were anesthetized with 0.08% MS222 and checked for the presence of GFP-positive cells under fluorescence microscopy (Leica Microsystems). Individuals with GFP-positive cells were reared separately in the incubator and fed with paramecium for two weeks, followed by *Artemia nauplii* until two months, then transferred to the aquarium and fed with dry flakes two times and blood worms once daily. Four weeks post-transplant, five fish were dissected to detect whether transplanted cells colonized the recipient gonad. Five months post-transplant, semen samples were collected from the mature recipients by stripping. Genomic DNA was extracted from the semen samples by the hotshot DNA extraction method²², followed by PCR amplification using GFP-specific primers, forward 5'-ACGTAAACGGCCACAAGTTC-3', and reverse 5'-AAGTCGTGCTGCTTCATG-3'³². Semen of a control giant danio was used as negative control for chimera genotyping.

In-vitro fertilization and spermatozoan concentration assessment. Zebrafish AB strain males and females were separately kept in a breeding chamber with the help of a barrier a day before spawning for fertilization. The same method was applied for giant danio males and females. On the spawning day, barriers were removed, and the females were observed for oviposition. Breeding pairs were first anesthetized with 0.08% MS222. Eggs from 7 to 8 zebrafish ovulated females were collected together in one Petri dish by gentle abdominal pressure. Similarly, two ovulated giant danio females were stripped to obtain the eggs. Semen samples from the control males and the germline chimera males were collected separately in the E400 extender (10 µl of the extender was used for each 1 µl of milk). A total of 10–20 µl of diluted sperm was used to fertilize ~100 eggs for each group (0.2–0.5 ml of dechlorinated water was used for sperm activation). Several combinations were made (see Table 2) in five replicates (five independent biological replicates) for the fertilization trial. The fertilization and the survival rate were recorded until day 5 for each combination, and the larvae derived from donor-derived sperm were subjected to GFP-specific amplification to detect germline transmission. A part of the progeny was reared until maturation and reproduced to generate F2 progeny.

Next, the semen samples were further diluted (1:10) to determine the sperm concentration for the donor-derived semen samples ($n = 5$) and controls ($n = 3$, for both donor and host). A Bürker Counting Chamber was used for spermatozoan counting.

Histology. The gutted torsos of 8-month-old morphant ($n = 10$) and control recipients were fixed in Bouin's fixative for 24 h and dehydrated in an ethanol series, embedded in JB-4 resin (JB4 embedding kit), using a plastic mold⁵⁸, and cut into 5 µm sections with a rotary microtome (Leica Biosystems). Sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin and examined under fluorescence microscopy (Olympus BX51).

A five-month-old germline chimera was dissected, and the entire testis was fixed with 4% PFA for 3 h at 4 °C and washed with 1× PBS. The fixed tissue was dehydrated with ethanol dilutions to preserve the GFP fluorescence (10 min for each dilution at 4 °C) and embedded in JB-4 resin. Twelve hours post-embedding, the tissue was sectioned and placed onto the SuperFrost slides with 5 min of air drying and mounted with fluoroshield mounting medium with DAPI. The prepared slides were analyzed by fluorescence microscopy immediately.

Sex-specific gene expression of sterile giant danio by RT-qPCR. Total RNA was extracted using TriReagent extraction and LiCl precipitation according to the manufacturer's instructions. The concentration of total RNA was determined using

a spectrophotometer (Nanodrop 2000, ThermoFisher Scientific), and the quality of RNA was assessed using a fragment analyzer (AATI, Standard Sensitivity RNA analysis kit, DNF-471). The cDNA was prepared using 500 ng of total RNA, 0.5 µl oligo dT and random hexamers (50 µM each), 0.5 µl dNTPs (10 mM each), 0.5 µl Maxima H Minus Reverse Transcriptase (Thermo Scientific), 0.5 µl recombinant ribonuclease inhibitor (RNaseOUT, Invitrogen), and 3 µl 5× Maxima RT buffer (Thermo Scientific) mixed with Ultrapure water (Invitrogen) to a final volume 15 µl. Samples were incubated for 5 min at 65 °C, 10 min at 4 °C, 10 min at 25 °C, 30 min at 50 °C, and 5 min at 85 °C followed by cooling to 4 °C. Obtained cDNA samples were diluted to a final volume of 100 µl and stored at -20 °C.

The qPCR reaction contained 5 µl of TATAA SYBR Grand Master Mix, 0.5 µl of forward and reverse primers mix (mixture 1:1, 10 µl each), 2 µl of cDNA, and 2.5 µl of RNase-free water. The reaction was conducted using the CFX384 Real-Time system (BioRad) with initial denaturation at 95 °C for 3 min followed by 40 cycles of denaturation at 95 °C for 10 s, annealing at 60 °C for 20 s, and elongation at 72 °C for 20 s. Melting curve analysis was performed to test reaction specificity, and only one product was detected for all assays. Male and female gonadal tissue was processed similarly to validate the specificity of RT-qPCR detection, and PCR products (50 ng) from MO samples were analyzed using standard Sanger sequencing with forward and reverse gene primers to confirm amplification specificity. The qPCR primers were designed from the available zebrafish mRNA sequences *sox9a* (Accession No. NM_131643.1), *cyp19a1a* (Accession No. NM_131154.3), *Vasa* (Accession No. NM_131057.1), and reference gene eukaryotic translation elongation factor 1 alpha 1, like 1 (*efl1l1*) (Accession No. NM_131263.1). For the primer list, see Supplementary Table 4.

Vasa-immunohistochemistry of the sterile giant danio gonad. Six-month-old giant danio morphants ($n = 3$) and controls were over-anesthetized, as mentioned. The gonads were removed and fixed with 4% PFA overnight at 4 °C, followed by dehydration and paraffin embedding. Sections were deparaffinized with xylene and with 96% and 70% ethanol, followed by washing twice with distilled water and PBS. The sections were subjected to antigen retrieval with sodium citrate buffer at 96 °C for 10 min, permeabilized with 0.3% triton in PBS for 10 min, and blocked with 10% goat serum. The sections were incubated with primary antibody Anti-DDX4 (ab13840) diluted to 1:300 with 4% goat serum in PBS overnight, followed by secondary antibody (goat anti-rabbit IgG (H + L) Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 488) at 1:500 dilution with PBS overnight, mounted with fluoroshield with DAPI and examined by fluorescence microscopy.

Statistics and reproducibility. Data on spermatozoan concentration, milt volume, and total sperm count were first checked for normal distribution using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Differences among three groups were calculated using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons with the adjusted $p < 0.05$, with data expressed as mean ± SD. For each group, data were collected from five biological replicates and repeated an average of three times. $p < 0.0001$ (****), $p < 0.002$ (**), and $p < 0.0332$ (*) unless stated otherwise. Sample size was determined based on the surviving germline chimera. No data was excluded. All statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad prism 9. Fertilization success of donor-derived sperm from germline chimera and control groups is presented as mean ± SD; data for each group was derived from five biological replicates (each biological replicate represents one independent fish). In-vitro fertilization was repeated three times for all the combinations. RT-qPCR data were derived from the gonadal tissue of ten MO-treated fish, three control males, and three control females. RT-qPCR was independently repeated two times to check the consistency of the results.

Reporting summary. Further information on research design is available in the Nature Portfolio Reporting Summary linked to this article.

Data availability

The source data for Fig. 2f is provided as Supplementary Table 1, and Fig. 4a–c is provided as Supplementary Table 3. The uncropped and unedited gel image for Fig. 3j is provided as Supplementary Fig. 2. All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this article and its Supplementary Information. All other data are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Author contributions

M.P. conceptualized and supervised the study, R.F. performed immunohistochemistry, R.S. performed qPCR and Sanger's sequencing for qPCR products. R.N. designed the study, performed the transplantation and other experiments, and wrote the manuscript. All authors helped in the manuscript editing and approved the final version.

Ethics declarations

The study was conducted at the Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters (FFPW), the University of South Bohemia in Ceske Budejovice, Vodnany, Czech Republic. The facility has the competence to perform experiments on animals (Act no. 246/1992 Coll., ref. number 16OZ19179/2016–17214). The Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee of the FFPW approved the methodological protocol of the current study according to the law on the protection of animals against cruelty (reference number: MSMT-6406/2019–2). The study did not involve endangered or protected species. Authors of the study (R.F. and M.P.) possess the Certificate of Professional Competence for designing experiments and experimental projects under Section 15d (3) of Act no. 246/1992 Coll. on the Protection of Animals Against Cruelty.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

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CHAPTER 3

GENOME-WIDE COMPARATIVE METHYLATION ANALYSIS REVEALS THE FATE OF GERM STEM CELLS AFTER SURROGATE PRODUCTION IN TELEOST

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My share of this work is about 70% (manuscript writing, experimental work, and data analyses).

RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Genome-wide comparative methylation analysis reveals the fate of germ stem cells after surrogate production in teleost

Rigolin Nayak^{1*}, Roman Franěk^{1,2}, Audrey Laurent³ and Martin Pšenička¹

Abstract

Background Surrogate production by germline stem cell transplantation is a powerful method to produce donor-derived gametes via a host, a practice known as surrogacy. The gametes produced by surrogates are often analysed on the basis of their morphology and species-specific genotyping, which enables conclusion to be drawn about the donor's characteristics. However, in-depth information, such as data on epigenetic changes, is rarely acquired. Germ cells develop in close contact with supporting somatic cells during gametogenesis in vertebrates, and we hypothesize that the recipient's gonadal environment may cause epigenetic changes in produced gametes and progeny. Here, we extensively characterize the DNA methylome of donor-derived sperm and their intergenerational effects in both inter- and intraspecific surrogates.

Results We found more than 3000 differentially methylated regions in both the sperm and progeny derived from inter- and intraspecific surrogates. Hypermethylation in the promoter regions of the protocadherin gamma gene in the intraspecific surrogates was found to be associated with germline transmission. On the contrary, gene expression level and the embryonic development of the offspring remained unaffected. We also discovered MAPK/p53 pathway disruption in interspecific surrogates due to promoter hypermethylation and identified that the inefficient removal of meiotic-arrested endogenous germ cells in hybrid gonads led to the production of infertile spermatozoa.

Conclusions Donor-derived sperm and progeny from inter- and intraspecific surrogates were more globally hypermethylated than those of the donors. The observed changes in DNA methylation marks in the surrogates had no significant phenotypic effects in the offspring.

Keywords Surrogate production, Epigenetic remodelling, Germ stem cells, Transplantation, CpG methylation

Background

Epigenetics plays a critical role in regulating the expression of genes during embryonic development and tissue differentiation in living organisms. The epigenome is defined as the structural adaptation of chromosomal regions [1], which maintains stable cellular processes in living individuals unless disrupted by external factors. The epigenetic modifications involve complex mechanisms governed by many structural and molecular regulators. The common mechanisms include (a) DNA methylation, (b) histone protein modification, and (c) non-coding RNAs [2]. Among all epigenetic marks, DNA

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methylation has been the most extensively studied [3]. The most common structural modification is the addition of a methyl group to the 5th carbon atom of a cytosine base, forming 5-methylcytosine (5-mC). The 5-mC modification in a DNA segment changes gene activity without changing the gene sequence [2, 4]. Hypermethylation in regulatory regions, such as promoters in the genome, is known to suppress transcription [5, 6]. In contrast, the loss of methylation marks, leading to hypomethylation, stimulates the expression of certain genes [7]. A methyl group-bound cytosine base is typically followed by guanine base in the sequence; this short segment is known as a CpG dinucleotide. In vertebrates, methylation most commonly occurs in the CpG context [8]. The percentage of methylated CpG sites varies by cell type [9] and individual organism. Any minor change to the epigenome can exert an impact on cellular function [10].

Surrogate production involves advanced reproductive biology-based biotechnology, which enables the production of donor-derived gametes via germline chimeras. Isolated germ stem cells (GSCs) from a donor species are implanted into the suitable sterile recipient (endogenous germ-cell-free individuals) to produce donor-derived gametes [11]. Surrogate production technologies have offered the possibility of preserving the germplasm of large-bodied commercially valuable species in smaller species with a shorter sexual maturation cycle [12, 13]. This technique provides a unique opportunity to cryopreserve maternal genetic information in fish, as neither fish eggs nor embryos can be cryopreserved. Therefore, there are efforts to develop techniques to conserve endangered species such as sturgeon [14–16]. Despite the recent advancements in this field, the practical application of this technology in aquaculture production is still questionable. Our understanding is limited to the morphological characteristics of the gametes and progeny produced via surrogacy. There are several questions pertaining to the reliability of this approach must be answered to maximize the possibility of applying surrogate production technologies in aquaculture. Epigenetic change is a major question associated with germ cell transplantation (GCT) that has never been reported. This mechanism is sensitive to internal and external environmental factors and can induce heritable phenotypical alterations [17]. Our knowledge of how and to what degree GCT can modify the epigenome (DNA methylation) of the donor germline is still scarce. Elucidating the epigenetic perturbations and their functional consequences will provide us insight into the reliability of the surrogate production approach.

Several factors may have a significant impact on the donor's methylome during GCT. Donor GSC is subjected to systematic procedures and is exposed to a variety of chemical compounds during surrogate production. The

complex gonadal tissue is then reduced to single cells and transplanted into recipients. Cell proliferation and differentiation of donor GSCs occur in the recipient's gonad after transplantation, supported by the gonadal somatic cells of the recipient. Very few of the hundreds of transplanted cells survive to be incorporated into the recipient gonad. In a previous study, Saito et al. [18] reported the size difference of the larvae produced by surrogate in zebrafish. Franek et al. [13] observed different morphological characteristics in male and female donor-derived gametes. Therefore, we hypothesize that the methylome of donor GSCs may undergo alterations in the recipient gonad and may thus lose or gain some crucial methylation marks. Considering these reports, it is now crucial to think beyond the morphological characteristics of the gametes produced by the surrogate parent. The number of methylation studies on donor-derived gametes produced via GCT is considerably lower than any other epigenetic study. A study of spermatogonia transplantation in mice has been reported, and it described the methylation of donor-derived spermatozoa and their offspring, but the results were limited to only a few imprinting genes [19]. In vitro culturing and transplantation of foetal germ cells have been conducted in mice, and the derived offspring were reported to exhibit growth abnormalities due to differential methylation [20], whereas fresh testicular tissue grafting into the recipients led to no epigenetic abnormalities in the germ cells or the offspring [21]. However, no information on methylation alterations in donor-derived gametes in fish has been reported.

It was previously reported that in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), DNA methylation pattern was preserved in the germline [22], and the paternal methylome was inherited by the embryos [23, 24], which is why it is crucial to decode the methylome of sperm produced by the surrogate. It has been shown that after endogenous germ cell depletion, all sterile zebrafish transdifferentiated into males [25, 26] and there was no female germline chimera after transplantation. Therefore, we used donor-derived sperm samples and progeny for this study. Sterilization to deplete the endogenous germ cells of the host species is a crucial step in surrogate production to prevent the production of recipient-derived gametes. Sterilization of a host can be achieved by chromosomal manipulation [27], gene knockdown, gene knockout [28], UV exposure [29], and chemical treatment [30]. In this study, we used vas:EGFP transgenic zebrafish as donors and two types of hosts: (1) dead end (*dnd*) gene knockdown (*dnd* gene is exclusively expressed in primordial germ cells (PGCs) and plays a crucial role in PGC migration to the gonadal ridge during embryonic development, *dnd*-morpholino (*dnd*-MO) prevents PGC migration by blocking the translation of dead end protein [31]; hence the recipient

becomes sterile with no endogenous germ cells) and (2) zebrafish and pearl danio (*Danio albolineatus*) hybrids (cross-breeding between two closely related species interferes with homologous chromosomal pairing during meiosis or induces mitotic arrest [32]).

Zebrafish have been used in many studies to produce germline chimeras [18, 33, 34] and may possibly be used in the future to resurrect the germplasm of certain valuable strains because of their small size, ease of breeding, and short maturation period. Our aim in this study was to answer the following questions: (1) Do the donor-derived gametes from surrogates present a different methylation pattern than the donor? (2) What are the differences in the methylation pattern between two different surrogates transplanted with the same donor GSCs? (3) Do the progeny derived from surrogates inherit altered methylation marks? and (4) Is the surrogate production approach reliable considering the epigenetic changes? To gain a greater understanding, we generated 24 whole-genome methylome datasets of sperm and progeny from two surrogates and donors at single-base resolution using whole-genome bisulfite sequencing (WGBS). We thoroughly investigated the differentially methylated regions by comparing the same sample types to identify any alterations in all three groups. We explored promoter methylation and investigated the potential biological and molecular function disruptions in the germline that are inherited by progeny.

Results

Data from transplantation

Transplantation was performed in three replicates for MO and hybrid recipients at 5 dpf because hatchlings possess relatively immature immune system and

transplanted spermatogonial cells are less likely to be immune rejected [35]. We screened the recipients at 14 dpf (day post-transplantation) to see the incorporation of donor spermatogonial cells and found an average of 45 and 35% of recipients were GFP-positive in MO and hybrid groups, respectively (Figure S1, Additional file 1). Upon maturation, an average of 40.4 and 21% of recipients from MO and hybrid groups produced donor-derived sperm (Table S1, Additional file 1), confirmed by GFP-specific PCR amplification, and no female germline chimera was observed in any group. Four adult germline chimera from each group were randomly selected for DNA methylation study (see Fig. 1 for the experimental design).

Surrogate groups show a strong correlation with donors at the whole-genome methylation level

We generated 24 whole-genome methylome datasets of ~30 Gb at single-base resolution for each sample (20× depth for each), with 70% of bases being covered at least 5 times (5×) and 50% covered at least 10× (genome coverage statistics is provided as Additional file 2). The bisulfite conversion rate was more than 99% for all the samples, with a mapping rate of approximately 60% of clean reads to the zebrafish reference genome GRCz11 (See Additional file 3 for mapping results). We calculated the average methylation level for all the genome cytosines in three different genomic contexts. We found that 87% of CpGs were methylated in the sperm samples for all three groups, and the average methylation level for the CHG and CHH contexts ranged between 0.35 and 0.4% (see Additional file 4, cytosine coverage in different contexts). In contrast, the progeny samples exhibited low CpG methylation levels, ranging between 79 and

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of the experimental designs. MO — morpholino-treated surrogate; dpf — day postfertilization. This figure was created with BioRender.com

81%, in which the CHH and CHG contexts accounted for 0.37 to 0.46%. When analysing the genome-wide methylation level, we did not observe a considerable difference between sperm and progeny samples in all three groups (Fig. 2A). Then, we examined methylation density at the whole-genome level. Methylation density showed high conservation among all groups and a trend similar to the methylation level, indicating a close relationship between methylation level and methylation density (Violin plots, Figure S2, Additional file 1). Since CHG and CHH methylation was negligible in all the samples, we focused only on CpG methylation in subsequent analyses.

Next, the correlation between replicates in each group was calculated using the Pearson correlation coefficient to determine closeness. The whole genome was divided into 2-kb bins, and the number of methylated cytosines (mCpG) was calculated for each bin. Replicates in each group showed a strong correlation, with r^2 value > 0.92 (Figure S3, Additional file 1). Next, we checked the correlation between groups of similar sample types. We compared the sperm samples, which showed high homogeneity with r^2 value > 0.91 , and the result was similar to the progeny samples, in which $r^2 > 0.9$.

Differential methylation analysis suggests no massive epigenetic remodelling in the surrogates

Data from the replicates were combined for the differential methylation analysis between comparison groups at the whole-genome level (Fig. 2B, Circos plot). We observed that the hypermethylation rate in the HybH and MOH groups was slightly higher than that of the DOH group, and the difference in the methylation level was high among all three compared groups. Similarly, the sperm samples from all three groups showed higher differences with a different methylation pattern in all 25 chromosomes. Surprisingly, the landscape of CpG methylation in all genomic functional regions followed a very similar pattern with methylation depletion at the

transcription start site (TSS) (Fig. 2C,D). Compared to those in other regions, introns and the repeat elements were hypermethylated and retained a similar shape in the plotted data for all the groups with no substantial difference. Compared to other genomic features, CpG islands (CGIs), which have been reported to predominate the promoter regions in vertebrates and to be involved in regulating gene expression [36, 37], were hypomethylated in all the samples and retained a similar methylation pattern in all studied groups. These results indicate that the sperm and progeny produced by the surrogates did not undergo a high degree of epigenetic remodelling.

DMRs in the compared groups reveal hypermethylation in both surrogates

Since we did not see any differences in the functional regions of the genome, we next investigated the differentially methylated regions (DMRs) in all groups. First, we calculated the number of DMRs in progeny samples across the genome. We found 3788 DMRs between the HybH and DOH, 3814 between the MOH and DOH, and 3766 between the MOH and HybH (Figure S4, Additional file 1). Then, we looked at hypomethylated (hypoDMR) and hypermethylated DMR (hyperDMR) in the compared groups. We annotated the DMRs according to their position in the genome (see Additional file 5 for the number of DMR distributions in all the genomic regions). More DMRs were found in introns and repeat elements than in other functional regions (Fig. 3A). When comparing HybH with DOH, we found more hyperDMRs in all the regions compared to the number of hypoDMRs. Then, we compared MOH and DOH and found almost the same number of both types of DMRs in all regions. However, the scenario was entirely different when we compared MOH with HybH, as we observed a higher number of hypoDMRs in all the regions, indicating higher methylation in HybH. Next, we calculated the methylation level of all the DMRs in the individual

(See figure on next page.)

Fig. 2 Global methylation pattern in all three groups. **A** Violin plots showing methylation levels in all three contexts. The whole genome was split into 10-kb sub-bins, and the methylation level was calculated for each context. The x-axis is labelled with the name of each sample, and the y-axis shows the methylation level. **B** Circos plots for methylation levels and their differences on each chromosome for the comparison groups. The chromosomes were divided into bins, and each bin's methylation level was calculated as follows: number of reads with mCs/(number of reads with mCs + number of reads with non-mCs). Description of the circos plot from outside to inside: methylation level for Group 1, colour denotes the methylation level (%); methylation level difference between groups, and the heatmap shows the difference (%); methylation level for Group 2, colour denotes the methylation level (%) and graph legends. The upper panel is for the progeny samples, and the lower panel is for the sperm samples. **C** The methylation level in the functional regions (promoter, utr5, exon, intron, utr3, CGI, CGI-shore, and repeat elements). After combining the samples with biological replicates, each functional region was divided into 20-kb bins, and the methylation level of each bin was calculated. The upper panel is for the progeny samples, and the lower panel is for the sperm samples. Graph legends contain the compared group names. **D** Methylation level 2 kb upstream of the TSS, 2 kb downstream of the TES, and the gene body. The upper panel is for the progeny samples, and the lower panel is for the sperm samples. Abbreviations: MOS — sperm derived from the MO chimaera; HybS — sperm derived from the hybrid chimaera; DoS — sperm derived from the donor; MOH — progeny derived from the MO chimaera; HybH — progeny derived from the hybrid chimaera; and DoH — progeny derived from the donor, $n=4$ biological replicates

Fig. 2 (See legend on previous page.)

Fig. 3 DMR methylation level and their distribution in the functional regions. **A** DMR distribution plot showing the different functional regions in the progeny sample comparison group. The x-axis shows the functional regions, and the y-axis shows the number of hyper-/hypoDMRs in each region. **B** Violin plot showing the DMR methylation level in the progeny samples in each comparison group. The x-axis shows the comparison group name, and the y-axis shows the methylation level. **C** DMR distribution in the sperm samples and **D** DMR methylation level of the sperm samples. The x-axis shows the comparison group name, and the y-axis shows the methylation level

groups (Fig. 3B). The median value of the methylation level of the DMRs associated with the HybH was higher than that in the MOH and DOH. When we evaluated the DMR distribution with a violin plot, most DMRs were found to have accumulated with a higher methylation level in MOH and HybH.

Next, we asked whether the DMRs in sperm samples were similar to those in the progeny groups. To this end, we found 3639 DMRs between the HybS and DOS, 3527 between the MOS and DOS, and 3708 between the MOS and HybS. We annotated the DMRs, assessed their distribution (Fig. 3C), and calculated the methylation levels (Fig. 3D). The DMR distribution in all the sperm groups was similar to that in the progeny groups. The violin plots show that most of the DMRs in HybS and MOS groups exhibited higher methylation levels compared to those in the DOS group (also see the cluster heatmap of the DMRs in Figure S5, Additional file 1). The median value was higher, suggesting that sperm samples from both surrogates carried more hyperDMRs than the donors. These results indicate that both sperm and progeny derived from the surrogates were hypermethylated compared to the methylation level of the donors.

Hypermethylation in promoters regions of protocadherin gene (*pcdh*) in MOH and HybS

Because most of the DMRs found were accumulated in intronic regions and repeat elements, we focused only on the promoter DMRs to see if any biological function was disrupted in the chimera groups (The list of significant DMPs between the compared group is provided as Additional file 6). Promoter regions are located within 1 kb from the TSS (-1 to 0). Methylation in the immediate vicinity of a TSS hinders transcription initiation, whereas methylation in the gene body does not and may even stimulate transcription elongation [37]. Hence, we extracted all the differentially methylated promoters (DMPs) and analysed their GO terms; terms with *p*-value less than 0.05 were considered to be significantly enriched (Figure S6, Additional file 1). To our surprise, in the comparison groups for the progeny samples, more DMPs associated with biological processes were significantly enriched in the MOH compared to HybH

and DOH. Biological functions such as homophilic cell adhesion, regulation of odontogenesis, and tooth mineralization were highly enriched in the MOH compared to HybH and DOH. We individually checked all the gene IDs for the promoters associated with this term in the Integrative Genome Viewer (IGV). The identified promoter regions encoded *pcdh1gc6*, *pcdh1g22*, *pcdh1g30*, *pcdh1g33*, *pcdh1g2*, and *pcdh1g31* (IGV Snapshots for *pcdh1g* DMPs, Fig. 4A). When visualizing individual replicates from each group of the progeny samples in IGV, the identified DMPs were found to be hypermethylated only in the MOH samples, and the pattern was consistent among the replicates. Next, we wondered whether these marks were present in the sperm samples. We compared the MOS and DOS groups and did not find significantly enriched DMPs related to these genes (Fig. 4B). When checking the methylation pattern in IGV for these DMPs, we see that HybS and DOS have similar methylation level, and the difference only arise in the progeny, where HybH and DOH show low methylation and MOH remains higher, suggesting that these loci in the HybH and DOH were demethylated while those in the MOH remained unchanged. These results indicated that hyperDMPs within the *pcdh* gene in MOH were transmitted through the germline.

We also found very few functions like cell–cell adhesion and homophilic cell adhesion enrichment for hyperDMPs in HybS, and the gene promoters targeted for these functions are *pcdh1g*, *pcdh2g*, and *pcdh1a* (Fig. 4C). However, the hybrid progenies were unaffected by this hypermethylation since we did not see any function enrichment in the GO analysis. We measured the mRNA expression levels for selected genes, such as *pcdh1g2*, *pcdh1g31*, *pcdh1g22*, and *pcdh1g33* by RT-qPCR (see Fig. 4D, individual data values for qPCR are provided in Additional file 7). However, We did not observe any significant difference in the gene expression level, which suggested that the hyperDMPs in *pcdh* did not affect the expression of these genes. Next, we analysed the hypoDMPs between MOH and DOH and found that functions such as regulation of angiogenesis, positive regulation of the developmental process, and positive regulation of vasculature development were significantly enriched. Angiogenesis

(See figure on next page.)

Fig. 4 *Hypermethylation in the pcdh gene.* **A** IGV snapshots showing multiple representative hyperDMPs in *pcdh1g* gene, with increased methylation in MOH samples compared to DOH. **B** IGV view of the same promoter regions showing no hyperDMPs between the MOS and DOS groups. **C** Predictive hyperDMPs between the HybS and DOS groups in *pcdh1a* and *pcdh2a* genes. The black lines below the sample tracks represent predicted DMP regions. DMP regions are also highlighted by red lines above the sample tracks, and RefSeq gene annotations are shown below the tracks. **D** Relative gene expression levels of *pcdh1g2*, *pcdh1g31*, *pcdh1g22*, *pcdh1g33*, and *itga5* normalized to housekeeping gene *eef1a111* (Individual data values for qPCR are provided in Additional file 7). Data are shown as mean \pm SD; One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons for data with Gaussian distribution and Kruskal–Wallis test for data with non-Gaussian distribution (for *pcdh1g2* data), *p* < 0.05, *n* = 5 biological replicates, ns = not significant

Fig. 4 (See legend on previous page.)

is the process of blood and lymphatic vessel formation during embryonic development [38]. DMPs in genes *itga5* and *itga6l* were found to be hypomethylated. Integrin alpha 5 (*itga5*) is essential for heart development [39], but RT-qPCR showed no significant difference in the mRNA expression levels for *itga5*. Next, we examined the hypoDMPs in the comparison groups HybH and DOH for enriched GO terms. We found very few basic enriched molecular functions like nickel cation binding, adenylate kinase activity, nucleotide kinase activity, and phosphotransferase activity. The promoters associated with these terms in the progeny samples were predicted to have transcription factor activity. The genes are *si:dkey-14o6.4*, *si:dkey-8o9.5*, and *si:dkey-54j5.2* (complete list is provided as Additional file 8). These HypoDMPs were not significant in the sperm samples of any surrogate groups.

Promoter hypermethylation in HybS reveals that MAPK/p53 pathway disruption leads to low-quality sperm production

Next, we investigated the KEGG (Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes) pathway enrichment for DMPs to determine whether any signalling pathway was disrupted.

Pathways with a *p*-value lower than 0.05 in Fisher's exact test were regarded as significant. When analysing the hypoDMPs between the MOH and DOH samples, we found that metabolic pathways, oxidative phosphorylation, and cardiac muscle contraction were highly enriched functional pathways (Figure S7, Additional file 1). The finding of cardiac muscle contraction enrichment was congruent with GO angiogenesis term enrichment in the MOH group. However, we did not find any significant pathway enrichment in the MOS group. Metabolic pathways are critical mechanisms, and oxidative phosphorylation is an essential function; enriched DMPs were found mainly in the mitochondrial genome (the complete list is provided as Additional file 9). Moreover, mitochondria are maternally inherited by progeny [40].

Interestingly, we found that MAPK/p53 signalling pathway and apoptosis functions were significantly enriched in the HybS group, and these functional consequences were due to hyperDMPs in the HybS. We observed the promoter region of the *Tp53* gene in the HybS and found it to be hypermethylated compared to that in the MOS and DOS (see Fig. 5A). We found that the apoptosis pathway was also altered due to hyperDMPs in the genes caspase, apoptosis-related cysteine peptidase (*casp*), BCL2

Fig. 5 Promoter hypermethylation in MAPK/p53 pathway genes. **A** IGV snapshots of the representative hyperDMPs between HybS and DOS within the gene *casp*, *bcl2l1*, *Tp53*, and *apaf1*. Black rectangle and Refseq gene annotations are shown below the tracks. **B** Relative gene expression levels of *Tp53*, *mapk12a*, *mapk8a*, *map2k2a*, *map4k2*, *apaf1*, and *bcl2l1* normalized to housekeeping gene *ef1a111* (Individual data values for qPCR are provided in Additional file 7). Data are shown as mean \pm SD; unpaired *t*-test for data with Gaussian distribution (*mapk12a*, *mapk8a*, *map2k2a*, and *bcl2l1* dataset) and the Mann–Whitney *U* test for data with non-Gaussian distribution (for *Tp53*, *apaf1*, and *map4k2* dataset) with adjusted *p* < 0.05, *n* = 4 biological replicates, asterisks represent significant difference between the groups, ns = not significant

like 1 (*bcl2l1*), and apoptotic peptidase activating factor 1 (*apaf1*). These genes are crucial for the activation of the apoptotic process. We then quantified the mRNA levels of selected MAPK/p53 pathway genes in the hybrid testes by RT-qPCR. A total of seven genes were quantified (*Tp53*, *mapk12a*, *mapk8a*, *map2k2a*, *map4k2*, *apaf1*, and *bcl2l1*), of which four genes *Tp53*, *mapk12a*, *map2k2a*, and *bcl2l1* showed a significantly lower level of gene expression compared to the donor (Fig. 5B).

In a previous comparison study by Franek et al. [41], donor-derived sperm from hybrid chimera showed low sperm velocity compared to that in the MO-treated chimeras, and the researchers speculated that the hybrids lacked a clearance mechanism. Nevertheless, the underlying molecular pathways were unknown. Our study revealed that promoter hypermethylation in hybrid potentially disrupted the function of MAPK kinases and the subsequent pathways, resulting in disturbed spermatogenesis. In our study, the in vitro fertilization rate of the donor-derived gametes from the hybrids with the control females was a deplorable success compared to MO and the donor males (Additional file 1, Table S2). Histological analysis of the untransplanted hybrid recipient gonad showed the presence of a few endogenous spermatozoa with developed testes (see Figure S8, Additional file 1). When analysing the sperm samples from the hybrid and MO chimera under the fluorescence microscope (Olympus fluorescence microscope), we observed the presence of spermatozoa without EGFP signal in the HybS. At the same time, the results from the MOS group were positive with EGFP expression in all the observed spermatozoa (See Figure S9, Additional file 1), which suggests that the semen samples of the HybS group are a mixture of both donor and recipient-derived sperm.

Discussion

We thoroughly assessed the whole-genome methylome of donor-derived sperm from two types of surrogates transplanted with zebrafish spermatogonial cells to address potential DNA methylation remodelling caused by GCT at single-base resolution using WGBS and compared it with donor sperm. We also compared the progenies derived from the surrogate and donor and examined any potential biological and molecular function disruption by the gain or loss of methylome. The growing interest in surrogate production tools has been frustrated by a lack of knowledge on gamete features at the methylome level and the consequences of these features. Germline cells interact with gonadal somatic cells at every stage of development, which supports their growth, proliferation, and differentiation into functional gametes [42]. This interaction can be different for the foreign cells when introduced into another individual/species. Unlike

genetic variation, epigenetic changes are more adaptable. When the environment changes, epigenetics changes more easily to adapt to the new environment. Some epigenetic changes are transient and can be reversed, while others are heritable and referred to as “epigenetic memory” [43]. Surprisingly, our results showed high homogeneity among all groups of similar sample types at the whole-genome level and even in functional genomic regions. The lower percentage of methylated CpG in the progeny samples implies that the embryonic genome is activated after fertilization and is part of the essential developmental process [44]. Sperm methylome remains hypermethylated with no transcriptional activities due to its compact packaging and less accessibility to the transcriptional machinery. Global hypermethylation in both surrogate sperm and progeny is thought to be caused by the influence of the microenvironment, such as stress to donor testicular cells during isolation, and spermatogenesis in a recipient’s gonad may be factors leading to the genome-wide hypermethylation in the chimeras and inherited by their offspring.

Hypermethylation of *pcdh* promoters in the MOH was associated with germline transmission. Previous studies have reported that sperm methylation marks are preserved in the germline and are stably transmitted to the next generation [22]. The clustered *Pcdh* genes code for a group of homophilic cell adhesion proteins known as protocadherins, which are required for cell–cell adhesion during vertebrate embryogenesis. These proteins are also essential for neural development in zebrafish embryos [45–48]. However, after hatching, we did not observe any disturbed phenotype in the larvae (Figure S10, Additional file 1). *pcdh*-gamma hypermethylation has previously been reported in human brain tumour tissues to be involved in transcriptional repression [49]. DMRs in *pcdh* genes have been found in zebrafish after bisphenol A exposure [50]. However, there is no direct report on *pcdh* hypermethylation affecting any biological function in the teleost. One might argue if *pcdh* promoter methylations are from the oocyte origin. This question is answered with the DOH and HybH methylome produced using the same females. In zebrafish, promoter hypermethylation is not sure to be the repressive mark for gene expression. On the contrary, it induces expression for a few genes [44]. However, all the hyper- and hypoDMPs in the MOH group do not seem to affect the gene expression, as confirmed by quantitative PCR. These results imply that differential methylation does not always alter gene expression. The correlation between methylation and gene regulation varies among types of cells, genotypes, and under different environmental conditions [51, 52]. This phenomenon also opens the discussion to what degree of differential methylation drives

the transcriptional changes and trait variability. Previous report suggests that methylation-dependent gene regulation activity is weak in human [53]. TALE-TET1 fusion proteins were used to induce target demethylation of CpG sites within the human *HBB* promoter, which revealed that demethylation of some CpG sites causally alters gene transcription. Demethylation did not affect *HBB* expression at other CpG sites in the same promoter [54], suggesting that CpG methylation-regulated gene expression is rather locus-specific for some genes to exert any expressional changes. Another study on zebrafish reported very little correlation between differential methylation and gene expression [55]. The relationship between differential methylation and gene expression is complex to be fully understood and requires extensive investigations.

Moreover, hybrid progenies were unharmed by the overall hypermethylation at the whole genome level because most DMRs were accumulated in the non-coding regions. Interestingly, our findings reveal the cause of low fertilization rate in the hybrid-chimera sperm due to discrepancies in the MAPK/p53 signal transduction pathway and apoptosis resistance in the recipient testes. Mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK) constitute the cascade of kinase proteins that control cell proliferation, differentiation, cell survival, and apoptosis through a signal transduction pathway in a coordinated manner [56]. Although we did not find altered gene expression levels in all the tested genes, we cannot rule out that *Tp53* transcript level was significantly lower together with other MAP kinases, *mapk12* and *map2k2a*, compared to the donor. p53 is a tumour suppressor protein believed to be activated after phosphorylation by MAP kinases. The activation of p53 further acts as a transcription factor for a group of genes that leads to the activation of the MAPK signal pathway [57]. Activation of p53 is also known to be involved in cell death and apoptosis. It is known that the MAPK pathway positively promotes the apoptotic pathway in the mice testis [58], which justifies the disruption of both pathways in HybS. In mammals, damaged germ cells are removed by apoptosis to prevent their differentiation into spermatozoa. Selective deletion of damaged germ cells is clearly an essential mechanism that protects a species genome [59]. A balance between the number of germ cells and Sertoli cells in the testis is also vital for the proper differentiation of germ cells and the production of fertile sperm. In the hybrid chimera, the damaged cells were the meiotic-arrested endogenous germ cells detected by the testis histology. The removal of damaged germ cells in the hybrid chimera was most likely suppressed due to apoptosis disruption caused by promoter hypermethylation of a group of genes, especially in the *Tp53* gene, resulting in an imbalance between the

number of germ cells and Sertoli cells and the production of undernourished spermatozoa. The promoter region of the *Tp53* gene has been previously reported to be significantly hypermethylated in cervical cancer patients [60], oral squamous cell carcinoma [61], and the significance of apoptosis for the development of normal spermatogenesis is explained in mice [62, 63]. Deficiency in *Tp53* gene expression has also led to abnormal spermatozoa production and reduced fertility in *p53*^{-/-} mice [64]. These observed alterations in DNA methylation in the hybrids may have been caused by interspecific hybridization. Nevertheless, these functional disruptions were not transmitted to the progeny, possibly because the functional donor-derived sperm fertilized the oocytes. There is the possibility that the embryos fertilized with the epigenetically abnormal spermatozoa are not viable because they cannot undergo early embryogenesis [65].

As reported by Franek et al. [41], *dnd*-MO-treated recipients were completely devoid of endogenous germ cells upon maturation and carried only gonadal somatic cells. A complete germ cell-free gonad supports the incorporation and proliferation of transplanted exogenous GSCs without its competition with endogenous germ cells. In contrast, the hybrids were not entirely germ-cell-free, as apparent by the histology of the gonad. Low fertility in hybrid chimera is described in two scenarios: In one case, the inefficient removal of damaged endogenous germ cells is due to disruption in the apoptosis pathway, affecting the growth of the introduced GSCs and leading to the generation of low-quantity donor-derived spermatozoa. In the second case, the production of abnormal recipient-derived spermatozoa. Our findings infer that inter- and intraspecific spermatogonial transplantation in zebrafish surprisingly did not severely affect the molecular characteristics of the donor-derived gametes. However, the sterilization of the host plays a vital role in transplanted germ cell development in the recipient gonad. It is essential to ensure the complete depletion of the endogenous germ cell. Notably, isolated testicular cells maintained their methylome integrity after exposure to several chemical compounds and enzymes during cell dissociation. Previous studies have shown that spermatogonial stem cells are more resistant to epigenetic alterations and retain their stability after transplantation in mice [66]. The epigenetic integrity of in vitro cultured human spermatogonial stem cells has been reported [65], and that explains the germ stem cells are more protected against epigenetic alterations. We presume that there is a strong selection bias after their transplantation into the host, which explains the reason that only a few cells survive to colonize the host gonad. For interspecific transplantation, this scenario for methylome pattern may differ if the host is phylogenetically farther species, which

needs to be investigated in the future. Our data cannot exclude the possibility that this scenario may vary from species to species and between different sterilization treatments. Zebrafish are highly polymorphic [67], and the methylation pattern can also differ between the individuals derived from the same parents. The advantage of using zebrafish as a model in this study is their lack of epigenetic reprogramming postfertilization. This makes them a suitable model to study epimutations caused by surrogate production and their intergenerational inheritance compared to other species like Japanese medaka, which undergo genome-wide reprogramming during embryonic development, and the majority of inherited marks are erased. However, whether the environmental stressor-induced DNA methylation marks escape the global epigenetic reprogramming in medaka is unclear. Our study is designed based on the most commonly used germ cell transplantation method. Gonial cell transplantation into larvae is easier than other methods, such as PGC transplantation. PGC isolation and transplantation are skill-sensitive and more complicated than gonial cell transplantation. Although PGC transplantation is well established in zebrafish, gonial cells are most commonly used for germ cell transplantation. There are several advantages of gonial cells over PGCs, including their abundance and transplantation into the hatchlings, which is considerably easier than PGC transplantation.

Moreover, we used freshly isolated testicular cells for transplantation in our study, and it will be interesting to understand the changes when transplanting the cryopreserved germ cells. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) is widely used as a cryoprotectant for the long-term storage of cell lines. In surrogate production techniques, cryopreserved germ stem cells are often used for transplantation. As per the previous study, DMSO significantly impacts genome-wide methylation in mouse embryonic cells and changes cell fate [68]. Future studies will explore the potential changes in the gamete produced by the transplantation of cryopreserved germ cells. The surrogate production technique is exploited to reduce the maturation period of some bigger species into fast-growing small fish [69, 70] and preserve the germplasm of endangered species [71].

Conclusions

In summary, our study addresses the question of DNA methylation alteration in surrogate production and their persistence in the offspring by using teleost model species zebrafish. We report that (1) the genome of donor-derived sperm and progeny from both chimeras showed higher levels of methylation than the donor, and the observed hypermethylation in the surrogates did not cause any functional or phenotypical abnormalities in the produced offspring, (2) protocadherin gamma was

the most affected gene in the MO chimera by promoter hypermethylation and transmitted to the F1 progeny, (3) hypermethylated *pcdh*-gamma promoters did not affect gene expression or larval development in zebrafish and (4) low fertility in the interspecific hybrid was a result of apoptosis resistance in the meiotic-arrested germ cell. Our data sets the stage for further research on surrogates produced by evolutionary, more divergent species. Future studies will focus on the donor-derived gametes produced by the transplantation of cryopreserved germ cells.

Methods

Recipient production and transplantation

Adult AB line (wild type) zebrafish for recipient production were obtained from the European Zebrafish Resource Center (EZRC, Germany). Transgenic Tg(*ddx4:egfp*) (ZDB-TGCONSTRCT-210809-1, referred to as *vas::EGFP*) strain expressing enhanced green fluorescence protein in the germ cells driven by the promoter of the germ-cell-specific *vasa* gene [72], from the University of Liege, Belgium, and maintained in our facility for several generations at 28 °C, 14/10-h light/dark photoperiod. All chemicals were procured from Sigma-Aldrich unless stated otherwise. The recipients were derived from the same parent (AB fish) and divided into two groups for *dnd*-MO injection (MO sequence 5′-GCTGGGCATCCATGTCTCCGACCAT-3′ [73], GeneTools, LLC) and hybrid production. *dnd*-MO (0.1 mM with 0.2 mM KCl) was injected into 1- to 2-cell-stage embryos. Hybrids were produced from AB females and pearl danio males as per the protocol described by Wong et al. [74]. Individual fish were first anaesthetized with 0.05% tricaine methanesulfonate (MS222). Then, the oocytes were collected from the ovulated AB females by applying gentle abdominal pressure, and milt was collected from the pearl danio (3-month-old) males; in vitro fertilization was then performed.

Testicular cell preparation from *vas::EGFP* donors and transplantation were performed according to the methods described by Franěk et al. [41] without any modification to the protocol. Three-month-old *vas::EGFP* males ($n=4$) were anaesthetized with an overdose of MS222. Testes were removed and washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) several times to remove the sperm and then fragmented into small pieces with a sterile scissor, followed by enzymatic digestion with 0.1% trypsin, 0.05% collagenase (Gibco) and 0.05% DNase in PBS for 60 min at room temperature (22–23 °C). The digestion was then terminated by Leibovitz -15 (L-15) medium supplemented with 20% foetal bovine serum (FBS) at a 1:1 ratio. The cell suspension was filtered through a sterile 30- μ m mesh filter (CellTrics) followed by centrifugation at 400 \times g for 10 min. The cell pellet was then resuspended in L-15 medium containing 10% FBS.

Five-day-old recipients (from two groups) were anaesthetized with 0.05% MS222 and placed on a Petri dish coated with 1% agar. The spermatogonia cell suspension was loaded into a pulled-glass capillary connected to a micromanipulator (M-152, Narishige, Japan) and a FemtoJet 4× microinjector (Eppendorf, Germany). The testicular cell suspension (500–600 cells, the number of sperm cells was not counted) was injected into the body cavity of each recipient. Fourteen days post-transplantation, recipients were evaluated under a fluorescence microscope (M205FA, Leica Biosystems) to detect the presence of GFP-positive cells. The individuals carrying GFP-positive cells were maintained at 28 °C in an incubator and fed with paramecium for 1 week and then with *Artemia nauplii* (Ocean Nutrition Europe). After 2 weeks in the incubator, they were transferred to a ZebTEC system (ZebTec Active Blue) and maintained until maturation with a dry diet (GEMMA Micro, Skretting) provided twice daily. Three months post-transplantation, milt samples from all the recipients were collected. Genomic DNA from the milt was extracted via the hotshot method [75] and validated with GFP-specific PCR primers (forward, 5′-ACGTAAACGGCCACAAGTTC-3′; reverse 5′-AAGTCGTGCTGCTTCATGT-3′) [76] using PPP master mix (TopBio). The amplification conditions were 94 °C for 5 min and 35 cycles of 94 °C for 30 s, 58 °C for 30 s, and 72 °C for 45 s, with a final extension of 72 °C for 5 min. The individuals showing positive amplification for GFP were considered to be germline chimeras.

DNA extraction and WGBS library preparation

Sperm from the vas::EGFP donor males and surrogate males ($n=4$, collected separately, three months old) were collected by stripping for each replicate individually according to the experimental design. Eggs from ovulated vas::EGFP females (3-month-old) were collected ($n=4$, pooled) and divided according to the number of replicates in each group. Progeny was generated for each group by fertilizing the eggs separately for each replicate. For the donor group (control), sperm samples were collected from males (DoS1, DoS2, DoS3, and DoS4) and their progeny, which were the newly hatched (5 dpf) larvae (DoH1, DoH2, DoH3, and DoH4). Similarly, for the MO-treated surrogates, sperm samples were collected to establish four replicates (MOS1, MOS2, MOS3, and MOS4), and the progenies were established groups named in series from MOH1 to MOH4. For hybrid chimeras, the sperm samples were established for groups named in series from HybS1 to HybS4, and the progenies were in groups named in series from HybH1 to HybH4. Each male in all three groups was considered to be one biological replicate. Hatched (5 days old) larvae and sperm samples were processed for genomic DNA

extraction using PureLink™ Genomic DNA Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The concentration of the extracted DNA was measured using a Qubit fluorometer (Qubit 4 Fluorometer, Invitrogen), and the quality to know the integrity of the DNA was checked using 1% agarose gel. Accel-NGS Methyl-Seq DNA Library Kit (Swift Biosciences) was used for WGBS library preparation. Firstly, the genomic DNA spiked with unmethylated lambda DNA (for calculating the bisulfite nonconversion rate) was fragmented into 200–400 bp. During the bisulfite conversion, unmethylated cytosine was converted into uracil, while methylated cytosine remained unchanged. Methylation sequencing adapters were ligated, followed by double-strand DNA synthesis. The library was subjected to size selection (library size of 300 bp) followed by PCR amplification and final purification. The purified libraries were sequenced on the Illumina Novaseq platform with PE150 sequencing strategy (Novogene, Beijing, China).

Histology of gonads

Histology was performed to evaluate the sterility of non-transplanted recipients. Three-month-old sterile recipients and intact controls ($n=3$ for each group) were anaesthetized with an overdose of MS222 and carefully degutted. The whole torso was fixed with Bouin fixative for 24 h, followed by dehydration with a series of ethanol dilutions, embedded in JB-4 resin (JB4 embedding kit), using a plastic mold, and cut into 5- μ m sections with a rotary microtome (Leica Biosystems). The sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin according to the method described by Sullivan-Brown et al. [77]. Stained sections were then imaged under the Olympus microscope (Olympus BX51) and analysed to identify germ cells.

RT-qPCR for hyper- and hypoDMP genes

Total RNA was extracted from the larvae (5 dpf, $n=5$ biological replicates) and the testis ($n=4$ biological replicates) using a PureLink RNA Mini Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific), followed by cDNA synthesis using WizzardScript™ RT FDmix (Wizbiosolutions). Synthesized cDNA samples were used as templates for RT-qPCR. PCR was performed with PowerTrack SYBR Green Master Mix on a QuantStudio™ 5 System (Applied Biosystems), and the PCR cycling conditions were as follows: 95 °C for 2 min, 40 cycles (95 °C for 15 s, and 60 °C for 60 s) followed by a dissociation curve. The housekeeping gene eukaryotic translation elongation factor 1 alpha 1 (*ef1a1*) was used as the reference gene to normalize the expression of target genes. The primer sequences used for RT-qPCR are presented in Additional file 10. The level of gene expression was calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method. Four to five biological replicates were

established for each group, and two technical replicates for each sample were established for RT-qPCR.

Raw data processing and mapping to the reference genome

Before analysis, the reference data for zebrafish, which included the reference sequence fasta file, the annotation file in gtf format, the GO annotation file, the description file, and the gene region file in bed format, were prepared. As for the bed files, we predict repeats through RepeatMasker (version 4.1.2), followed by getting CGI track from the genome using cpGIslandExt. Bismark software (version 0.16.3, [78]) was used to perform alignments of bisulfite-treated reads to the zebrafish reference genome GRCz11. The reference genome was first transformed into a bisulfite-converted version (C-to-T and G-to-A) and then indexed using bowtie2 [79]. Sequence reads were also transformed into fully bisulfite-converted versions (C-to-T and G-to-A conversions) before they were aligned to similarly converted versions of the genome in a directional manner. Sequence reads that produced the best unique alignment from two alignment processes (the original top and bottom strand) were then compared to those from the normal genomic sequence, and the methylation state of all cytosine positions in each read was inferred. The reads that aligned to the same regions of the genome were regarded as duplicated reads. The sequencing depth and coverage were summarized using deduplicate reads. The results of methylation extraction (bismark_methylation_extractor) were transformed into bigWig format for visualization using the IGV browser. The sodium bisulfite nonconversion rate was calculated as the percentage of cytosine residues sequenced at cytosine reference positions in the lambda genome.

Methylation level estimation

The sequence was divided into multiple bins of size 10 kb for the methylation level calculation. The sum of the methylated and unmethylated read counts in each window was calculated. The methylation level (ML) for each window or C (cytosine) site shows the fraction of methylated cytosines (mC) and is defined as Eq. 1. The calculated ML was further corrected on the basis of the bisulfite nonconversion rate as described in a previous study [80]. Given the bisulfite nonconversion rate “*r*”, the corrected ML was estimated as Eq. 2.

$$ML(C) = \text{reads}(mC) \div \text{reads}(mC) + \text{reads}(C) \quad (1)$$

$$ML(\text{corrected}) = ML - r \div 1 - r \quad (2)$$

DMR analysis

Differentially methylated regions (DMRs) were identified using DSS software [81–83]. The core of DSS is a new dispersion shrinkage method for estimating the dispersion

parameter from Gamma-Poisson or Beta-Binomial distributions. According to the distribution of the DMRs throughout the genome, the genes related to DMRs were identified as genes with a gene body region (from TSS to TES) or promoter region (upstream 2 kb from the TSS) that overlaps with a DMR. The DMR filtering command and parameters are as follows: smoothing=TRUE, smoothing.span=200, delta=0, p.threshold=1e-05, minlen=50, minCG=3, dis.merge=100, pct.sig=0.5. Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis of genes related to DMRs was implemented with the GOSeq R package [39], in which gene length bias was corrected. GO terms with corrected *P* values less than 0.05 were considered to be significantly enriched. Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG, <http://www.genome.jp/kegg>) is a database resource for understanding high-level functions and utilities of the biological system [84]. We used KOBAS software [39] to test the statistical enrichment (*P*<0.05) of DMR-related genes in KEGG pathways.

Statistical analysis

Data for relative gene expression was first checked for normal (Gaussian) distribution with the Shapiro–Wilk test. Differences among the three groups were calculated using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s multiple comparisons for normally distributed samples and the Kruskal–Wallis test for data with non-Gaussian distribution. Unpaired *t*-test was used to calculate the significance between the two groups for normally distributed data and the Mann–Whitney *U* test for data with non-Gaussian distribution with the adjusted *p*-value < 0.05. The statistical analysis for RT-qPCR data was performed using GraphPad Prism 9.

Abbreviations

HybS	Sperm derived from the hybrid chimera
HybH	Progeny derived from the hybrid chimera
DoS	Sperm derived from the donor
DOH	Progeny derived from the donor
MOS	Sperm derived from the MO chimera
MOH	Progeny derived from the MO chimera
5-mC	5-Methylcytosine
GSC	Germ stem cell
MO	Morpholino antisense nucleotide
PGC	Primordial germ cell
WGBS	Whole-genome bisulfite sequencing
GO	Gene Ontology
KEGG	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes
TSS	Transcription start site
TES	Transcription end site
TE	Transposable element
DMP	Differentially methylated promoter
DMR	Differentially methylated region
GCT	Germ cell transplantation
IGV	Integrative Genomics Viewer
ML	Methylation level
mC	Methylated cytosine
MAPK	Mitogen-activated protein kinases

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12915-024-01842-z>.

Additional file 1: Figure S1. vas:EGFP testicular cell transplantation into the sterile recipients. **Table S1.** Data from transplantation. **Figure S2.** Violin plots for methylation density in all three contexts. **Figure S3.** Correlation analysis for CG context. **Figure S4.** Venn plot for the number of DMRs in all the compared groups. **Figure S5.** Cluster heatmap for DMR methylation level. **Figure S6.** GO term enrichment between the compared groups. **Figure S7.** KEGG enrichment scatter plot for DMP-related pathway. **Table S2.** In vitro fertilization success of the germline chimeras and the donor. **Figure S8.** Images of the testis histological sections. **Figure S9.** EGFP expression in the sperm samples. **Figure S10.** Progenies derived from donor-derived sperm show no phenotypical alterations.

Additional file 2. The statistics of the genome coverage. File containing the genome coverage statistics for WGBS data.

Additional file 3. Summary of mapping results. File containing mapping results of the sequencing reads to the reference genome.

Additional file 4. The coverage statistics of cytosine in three different contexts. File containing the summary of the total percentage of cytosine bases covered in three different contexts.

Additional file 5. Summary of the DMR distribution in different genomic regions. File containing the distribution summary of the DMRs between the compared groups in different genomic regions.

Additional file 6. The number of significant DMPs in all the compared groups. File containing the number of significant DMPs in all the compared groups.

Additional file 7. Individual data values for qPCR. File containing relative gene expression data values for the individual samples.

Additional file 8. Gene ontology analysis of DMPs. File containing GO functional enrichment analysis of observed DMPs between all the compared groups.

Additional file 9. KEGG signaling pathway analysis of DMPs. File containing KEGG signaling pathway enrichment analysis of observed DMPs between all the compared groups.

Additional file 10. Primer sequences used in RT-qPCR. File containing the primer sequences used in RT-qPCR.

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Authors' contributions

MP conceptualized and supervised the study. RF performed the transplantation and provided the biological samples, RN performed the experiments, data analysis, and wrote the manuscript. AL helped with the manuscript review. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Availability of data and materials

The raw data files and the processed methylation data are publicly available at the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) under accession number GSE212876 [85]. Supplementary figures are provided in Additional file 1, and other data supporting the conclusions of this article are provided in Additional files 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10. All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article and its supplementary information files.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The study was conducted at the Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters (FFPW), the University of South Bohemia in Ceske Budejovice, Vodnany, Czech Republic. The facility has the competence to perform experiments on animals (Act no. 246/1992 Coll., ref. number 16OZ19179/2016–17214). The Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee of the FFPW approved the methodological protocol of the current study according to the law on the protection of animals against cruelty (reference number: MSMT-6406/2019–2). The study did not involve endangered or protected species. The co-authors of the study (RF and MP) own the Certificate of Professional Competence for designing experiments and experimental projects under Sect. 15d (3) of Act no. 246/1992 Coll. on the Protection of Animals Against Cruelty.

Consent for publication

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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CHAPTER 4

PARTIAL GONADECTOMY: A NEW APPROACH TO OBTAIN GERMLINE STEM CELLS FOR TRANSPLANTATION WHILE PRESERVING THE DONOR

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Partial gonadectomy: A new approach to obtain germline stem cells for transplantation while preserving the donor

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Abstract

Surrogacy involves the transplantation of germline stem cells from the donor into the recipient of interest to produce germline chimera. It offers many scopes of restoration of lines from cryopreserved germ stem cells and faster propagation of species with a long maturation time with the help of a surrogate. However, studies reported to date always involved donor sacrificing prior to germ cell collection. Such a practice can significantly hamper the decision of whether surrogacy should be employed as a propagation method for valuable species. Here, we show a non-lethal approach to obtain germline stem cells from adult zebrafish males. We confirm that non-lethally collected spermatogonial cells successfully colonized the recipient gonad and gave rise to donor-derived sperm and, subsequently, viable progeny. Testicular tissue donors showed no mortality after partial gonadectomy in zebrafish. Importantly, their reproductive characteristics were not compromised, and gonads were regenerated. Turquoise killifish males showed no significant differences in their reproductive output compared to the controls post partial gonadectomy. Our study presents robust evidence that surrogate reproduction can be leveraged by partial gonadectomy in small-bodied fish (~0.5g) while keeping the donor alive and preserving its breeding value. Therefore, we expect that its application in large aquaculture species is feasible and will serve as a viable alternative to the commonly used lethal approach for donor cell collection. Afterward, gonadal tissue donors can still be involved in the breeding cycle while their germ cells are safely stored in liquid nitrogen or propagated through surrogates.

Keywords: *Germ cell, transplantation, surrogate production, gonadectomy, zebrafish, turquoise killifish*

Introduction

Germline stem cells (GSCs) are the progenitors of gametes. GSCs are bipotent and can transdifferentiate into both sperm and oocyte depending on the sex of the recipient (Okutsu et al., 2006a). The surrogate production approach utilizes this advantage to produce germline chimera in closely related species by transplanting GSCs in the sterile recipient, also known as a surrogate. Germ stem cell transplantation (GCT) in fish is a widely used approach to produce germline chimera for various applications such as genetic resource preservation of threatened species (Lee et al., 2015; Marinović et al., 2019; Franěk et al., 2021), and shortening the generation time (Hamasaki et al., 2017). GCT has been conducted in many species, such as

salmonids (Hattori et al., 2019; Iwasaki-Takahashi et al., 2020), sturgeon (Pšenička et al., 2016), cyprinids (Octavera and Yoshizaki, 2019; Franěk et al., 2021), and other marine species (Morita et al., 2015; Yoshikawa et al., 2017; Ren et al., 2021). All studies reported for the GCT have involved sacrificing many donor individuals to isolate the gonad in order to obtain transplantable GSCs. Some species, like Salmonids and sturgeon, are highly valuable and take many years to reach sexual maturation. Sacrificing the whole fish to obtain a few cells each time for transplantation can cause a significant loss of breeding value. In addition, the amount of GSCs required for transplantation depends on the size and number of the recipient larvae. In bigger species like rainbow trout, approximately 5,000 to 15,000 Type-A spermatogonia were reportedly transplanted into each recipient to generate germline chimera (Okutsu et al., 2006; Lee et al., 2013; Iwasaki-Takahashi et al., 2020), whereas Franěk et al. (2019) found out that single zebrafish testes can be sufficient to transplant approximately 50 zebrafish larvae. However, there is no direct assessment report on the optimal number of GSC required for germline chimera generation, and it may vary among species. Moreover, GCT is considered to be practiced for aquaculture species in the future, and transplantation involving a larger donor species can cause a waste of resources because only a small part of the gonad may be sufficient to obtain transplantable GSCs.

Male and female germ cells take distinct paths during oogenesis and spermatogenesis. Spermatogonium divides mitotically and enters meiosis at a later developmental stage (Zhao and Garbers, 2002). In GCT, male donors are more frequently used because of the abundance of spermatogonial stem cells in the testis. In contrast, female germ cells enter meiosis at an early developmental stage (Okutsu et al., 2006), and the immature ovary has a lower proportion of oogonia to the overall mass of the ovary due to growing oocytes occupying most of the tissue (Ichida et al., 2019). This is why the male broodstock of the desired donor species may get overused with time to obtain transplantable germ cells for surrogate production. To preserve the breeding value while securing genetic resources simultaneously, our study is designed to test a new approach to non-lethal gonad collection using partial gonadectomy.

Partially removed testis from the donor can be used to isolate thousands of testicular cells for GCT. The presence of germ stem cells in gonads ensures the regeneration of the resected testicular segment (Nóbrega et al., 2010), providing an opportunity to use the gonadectomized males for breeding in the future (Pronina and Petrushin, 2019) at the same time producing donor-derived gametes via germline chimera. GCT involves several crucial steps, such as sterilization of recipients, obtaining viable cells for transplantation, and completion of the whole lifecycle of transplanted recipients. Therefore, the success rate expressed by a number of recipients producing donor-derived gametes relies on many variables. Current practice transplantation requires the sacrifice of donors for cell preparation, while the success of producing germline chimeras is hardly predictable. Considering this, introducing how to collect cells non-lethally will undoubtedly possess a strong advantage over the currently used lethal approach.

In this study, we have performed partial gonadectomy in two small species, zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) and African turquoise killifish (*Nothobranchius furzeri*). In the zebrafish study (Figure 1), we have used vas::EGFP zebrafish male donors and AB (wild type) recipients and mainly focused on the following key points: 1) to develop a procedure for partial gonadectomy ensuring their survival and reproductive performance, 2) to record the germline chimera production efficiency. In the second study using turquoise killifish males, we performed partial

gonadectomy in the males and later recorded their reproductive performances. Here, we have established, for the first time, a unique method to isolate the transplantable testicular cells from living donor individuals followed by successful donor-derived sperm from the germline chimeras without compromising the donor's reproductive characteristics.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the study design in zebrafish. This figure is created using Biorender.com.

Methods

Fish husbandry and recipient production

Vas::EGFP zebrafish lines were originally procured from the University of Liege, Belgium, and AB wildtype strains were procured from KIT, Germany. Vas::EGFP zebrafish is the transgenic line where the EGFP reporter gene is under the control of *vas* promoter and expressed exclusively in germ cells (Krøvel and Olsen, 2002). Zebrafish lines were held in our facility for several generations at 28 °C, photoperiod 14L:10D, and fed with *Artemia nauplii* and a dry diet. AB line broodstocks were prepared for spawning by separating males and females in a breeding chamber the night before. The following day, barriers were removed, and the mating pairs were allowed to spawn for up to 30 minutes. Embryos were collected immediately after spawning from the breeding chamber and transferred to a clean Petri dish. Primordial germ cell migration was prevented by dead-end antisense morpholino nucleotide (*dnd*-MO, 5'-GCTGGGCATCCATGTCTCCGACCAT-3' (Weidinger et al., 2003). 1M stock of *dnd*-MO was diluted with 0.2M KCL to a final concentration of 0.1M and injected into the embryos at the 1–2 cell stage through the chorion (Ciruna et al., 2002). The injected embryos were held at 28 °C until hatching with a daily clean water change.

Gonadectomy in zebrafish

One-year-old vas::EGFP zebrafish ($n = 10$) were anesthetized with 0.05% of tricaine methanesulfonate (MS222). The fish was pat dry gently with a Kimwipe. The incision was intended to be above the cranial end of the ventral fin. Therefore, scales in the area were removed to ease the incision and subsequent sutures. The skin was lifted by forceps, and a small vertical cut in the lateral muscle was made by fine, sharp forceps towards the dorsum. Then, the body cavity was approached by scissors with dull tips to minimize the risk of damaging internal organs or blood vessels. The overall length of the incision was about 3 mm. The male gonads can be easily identified by their milky white colour and visible spermatogenic cysts at high magnification. The testes were gently grabbed by forceps, and its cranial segment

was resected while the caudal end was left intact to not damage sperm ducts. The incision was closed using nylon sutures and ultra-fine forceps when both sides of the incision were pierced, and nylon thread was pulled through and fixed by a triple knot. The overall surgery time for each fish was less than five minutes. After surgery, males were placed in well-aerated aquaria with 1% NaCl with subsequent water changes without saline over three days.

Gonadectomy in killifish and reproduction

Partial gonadectomy was performed on 6-week-old males in an identical manner as described above for zebrafish. After the recovery period, breeding tanks for both operated and same-operated males were set up. One male was placed with two females, and eggs were collected on a weekly basis for three consecutive weeks. Developing and dead embryos were counted and expressed as developmental rates.

Transplantation in zebrafish

Testicular tissue was isolated from all the donors ($n = 10$) and pooled. The pooled tissue was cut into pieces with a sterile scissor and washed with PBS to remove the excess amount of sperm. The testicular fraction was then subjected to enzymatic digestion with 0.1% trypsin (trypsin from porcine pancreas), 0.05% collagenase Type I (collagenase from *Clostridium histolyticum*), and 0.5% DNase I (DNase I from bovine pancreas) in PBS for 50 minutes at 22–23 °C on a shaker. Enzymatic digestion was terminated after 50 minutes by adding one volume of L-15 medium (Leibovitz's L-15 Medium) supplemented with 20% foetal bovine serum (FBS). The cell suspension was filtered through a 45 μm pore size filter (CellTrics) and centrifuged at 400 g for 10 minutes. The cell pellet was resuspended with L15 and transplanted into the 5dpf AB sterile recipients.

Four males from the same age group were gonadectomized similarly to count the number of spermatogonial cells. Testis fractions were obtained from each male and processed separately for testicular cell isolation, as described above. Isolated cell suspension was diluted at a 1:2 ratio with Trypan blue (Cytiva HyClone™) solution for viable spermatogonial cell counting using a Bürker chamber. Cells were counted two times at an average to ensure the reproducibility of the data.

Reproductive performance assessment in zebrafish gonadectomized males

One-year-old vas::EGFP males (controls, non-gonadectomized males) and females were kept in breeding chambers a night before the spawning. The barriers were removed the following day, and the mating pairs were closely monitored for oviposition. Oviposited females and males were immediately transferred to the lab. First, ten males were anesthetized with 0.05% of MS222. Semen samples were collected separately in the E400 extender at a 1:10 ratio by gentle abdominal pressure, and the semen volume was recorded for each male. Similarly, semen samples from ten gonadectomized donors three months post-gonadectomy ($n = 10$ biological replicates) were collected in separate vials, and the volumes were recorded. Next, eggs were collected from the ovulating females ($n = 10$, pooled) by gentle abdominal massage in a clean petri dish. Half the volume of the collected semen from the control males and the gonadectomized donors was used for in vitro fertilization separately for each individual to determine the fertilization rate. The fertilization rate was determined according to the embryo survival rate until the segmentation period. The remaining semen samples were used for sperm concentration assessment using a Bürker chamber for the control males ($n = 10$ biological replicates) and for the gonadectomized males ($n = 10$ biological replicates).

Germline chimera assessment in zebrafish

Three months post-transplant, semen samples were collected from the surviving recipients in the E400 extender at a 1:10 ratio by gentle abdominal pressure (Matthews et al., 2018). Collected sperm samples were checked for the presence of EGFP under fluorescence and by EGFP-specific PCR amplification using forward primer 5'- ACGTAAACGGCCACAAGTTC -3', and reverse 5'- AAGTCGTGCTGCTTCATG -3. The amplification conditions were 94 °C for 5 minutes and 35 cycles of 94 °C for 30 seconds, 58 °C for 30 seconds, and 72 °C for 45 seconds, with a final extension of 72 °C for 5 minutes. One adult recipient was dissected to observe the gonadal development and the GFP expression in the testis.

Histology

After the sperm concentration and fertilization assessment, all gonadectomized donors were sacrificed by overdose of Tricaine. Males were dissected, and the regenerated part of the testis was photographed under a fluorescence microscope. Next, the regenerated part of the left testis was carefully taken and fixed with Bouin's solution for 24 hours, and similarly, the right testis was fixed separately with Bouin's solution for 24 hours. After fixation, the testis was dehydrated with a series of ethanol solutions followed by infiltration and resin embedding using the JB4 Embedding Kit (Sullivan-Brown et al., 2011). Next, the tissue was cut into 5 µm thick serial sections using a rotary Microtome. The tissue sections were stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin and analyzed under a BX63 Olympus Fluorescence microscope.

Statistical analysis

Data for sperm concentration, milt volume, total sperm count, and fertilization rate were first checked for normal distribution using Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The data with normal distribution were analysed with a t-test, and data that did not pass the normality test were analysed with the Mann-Whitney test.

Results

Partial gonadectomy in zebrafish males does not affect survival and reproductive performance

We monitored the gonadectomized males after non-lethal testis collection for up to three months. All testicular tissue donors (n = 10) survived partial gonadectomy. Next, we aimed to see the reproductive performance of all the donors and compare them with the normal vas::EGFP transgenic males that are non-gonadectomized from the same age group (one-year-old). The donors were reproduced three months post-gonadectomy to check the milt volume, sperm concentration, and fertilization rate. The reproductive outputs of the donors were not significantly different from the normal males (**Figure 2A-D**). Then, the donors were dissected to see if the left testis was regenerated, and we observed an intact structure of the left testis in all the dissected individuals with a very prominent GFP expression near the dissected part of the left testis (**Figure 2J-J'**, the area is depicted by a yellow rectangle). Histology of the depicted region showed the presence of a lower population of final-stage spermatids compared to the undissected right testis. The regenerated part of the left testis mainly accumulated by spermatogonia type B (early and late) and meiotic spermatocytes, while the right testis was mostly occupied by the spermatids. These results indicate that the newly regenerated part has initiated spermatogenesis and possesses the characteristics of an immature testis.

Table 1. The number of testicular cells in the partially resected zebrafish testis.

	Length of resected segment (in mm)	Number of viable cells/ml
Male 1	1.98	95.9×10^5
Male 2	1.99	80.9×10^5
Male 3	2.11	72.3×10^5
Male 4	2.49	132.5×10^5

Figure 2. Gonadectomy and germline chimera production in zebrafish.

A-D) Reproductive performance by the donor individuals, sperm concentration, milt volume, total sperm count, and fertilization success, respectively, the data represent the mean with 95% confidence interval, $P < 0.05$, $n = 10$. **E)** A donor during the partial removal of the left testis, **F)** The incision area is sutured after the partial resection, **G-H)** Partially gonadectomized donor after three months of surgery, the incision area is healed completely, **I-J)** Regenerated region of left testis depicted by the yellow rectangle expressing a prominent signal for GFP when compared to other parts of the testis. **I'-J')** Higher magnification of the depicted area. **K-K')** The transverse section of the depicted area in the left testis has orange arrowheads indicating spermatogonia, green arrowheads indicating primary spermatocytes, and red arrowheads indicating spermatozoa. **L-L')** The right testis shows a large population of spermatozoa, indicated by red arrowheads. **M)** Sperm derived from the adult germline chimera under brightfield, and **M')** The same milt sample under the FITC filter shows the GFP expression in the spermatozoa. **N)** Three-month-old dissected adult germline chimera under brightfield, **N')** Testis with GFP expression under FITC filter. BF – brightfield. Scale bars, E, F, G, H, I and J = 1mm, I', J', K and L = 200 μ m, K' and L' = 100 μ m, M and M' = 20 μ m, N and N' = 1mm.

Reproduction outputs in killifish

We observed no mortality after partial gonadectomy in the killifish males. Fourteen days post-gonadectomy, the gonadectomized males were spawned for three consecutive weeks to record their reproductive performance. The developmental rate of the embryos was comparable to that of the control males (**Figure 3**), suggesting that the partial gonadectomy did not compromise sperm production.

Figure 3. Killifish reproduction post-partial gonadectomy.

Killifish males ($n = 7$ biological replicates) fourteen days later partial gonadectomy. Each male was paired with two females and spawned. Spawning was repeated three times to get the average developmental rate of the eggs laid for each gonadectomized male. The data represent the mean with SD, $P < 0.05$, $n = 7$. G-Males – Gonadectomized males, ns – Not Significant.

Germline chimera in zebrafish

The survived transplanted recipients ($n = 63$) were checked for the presence of vas::EGFP cells after ten days of transplantation, and 16% ($n = 10$) of the recipients contained GFP-positive cells. Three months post-transplantation, the recipients were stripped to collect the semen samples, and only four recipients produced the milt containing donor-derived sperm confirmed by GFP-specific PCR amplification (data not shown) and the expression of GFP under a fluorescence microscope (**Figure 2M-M'**). One of the confirmed germline chimeras was dissected to see the testis development and vas::EGFP expression under a fluorescence microscope. We observed unilaterally developed testis with prominent GFP expression (**Figure 2N-N'**)

Discussion

Here, we have reported the regeneration of the testis after partial gonadectomy in two small-bodied species, zebrafish and turquoise killifish, with zero mortality. We have developed a new approach to obtain germ stem cells from the donor without sacrificing the fish by performing a non-lethal partial gonadectomy in zebrafish. Although zebrafish is a small-bodied fish model, we achieved 100% survival in operated tissue donors. The isolated cell suspension from the donors was enough to transplant 63 recipients. We observed that the dissected part of the left testis was capable of complete regeneration in zebrafish. Interestingly, we could easily distinguish the regenerated part of the gonad by visual inspection when strong EGFP expression was confirmed, suggesting a large proportion of early-stage germ cells. Subsequently, histology of the regenerated region shows a low population of spermatozoa.

Partial gonadectomy did not compromise the milt volume or the total sperm count in the gonadectomized individuals compared to the non-gonadectomized controls of the same age. This study shows that partial gonadectomy in zebrafish could not alter the quality or quantity of sperm production. The success of germline chimera production in fish is unpredictable, with a risk of losing the donor species in each transplantation. This approach offers a unique opportunity to keep the donor alive. Moreover, the germ stem cells have the ability to regenerate again in the partially gonadectomized donors, which provides another chance to prepare the donor cells if the transplantation fails to work in the first trial. Gonadectomy has previously been reported in European catfish *Silurus glanis* to isolate gonad *In vivo* in order to obtain milt for *in vitro* fertilization without urine contamination (Pronina and Petrushin, 2019) and to study the sex steroid in Japanese medaka *Oryzias latipes* (Royan et al., 2020). Since the surrogate production approach has immense potential for gene banking of endangered species like sturgeon (Pšenička et al., 2015) and commercially valuable species, common carp (Franěk et al., 2021), the combination of partial gonadectomy and transplantation may provide new insight for the research community aims at germline chimera generation. Future studies may assess the potential of gonad regeneration in larger species that have longer maturation periods, like sturgeon, salmonids, and common carp.

Conclusion

Partial gonadectomy in zebrafish did not compromise the reproductive performances and provided a suitable alternative for spermatogonial cell isolation for germline chimera production without sacrificing the donors. Gonadectomy in killifish males did not affect fertility, and the developmental rate of the laid eggs was comparable to that of non-gonadectomized males.

Declarations

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Ethics approval and consent to participate

The study was conducted at the Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters (FFPW), the University of South Bohemia in Ceske Budejovice, Vodnany, Czech Republic. The facility has the competence to perform experiments on animals (Act no. 246/1992 Coll., ref. number 16OZ19179/2016–17214). The Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee of the FFPW approved the methodological protocol of the current study according to the law on the protection of animals against cruelty (reference number: MSMT-6406/2019–2). The study did not involve endangered or protected species. Authors of the study (RF and MP) own the Certificate of professional competence for designing experiments and experimental projects under Section 15d (3) of Act no. 246/1992 Coll. on the Protection of Animals Against Cruelty.

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Consent for publication

Not applicable

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors' contributions

RN performed the experiments and data analysis and wrote the manuscript. RF conceptualized and supervised the study and performed some experiments. MP helped with manuscript review and editing. All the authors read and approved the manuscript. All the authors read and approved the manuscript.

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CHAPTER 5

GENERAL DISCUSSION

ENGLISH SUMMARY

CZECH SUMMARY

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

TRAINING AND SUPERVISION PLAN DURING THE STUDY

CURRICULUM VITAE

General discussion

Xenogenic transplantation using commonly used model species, zebrafish were transplanted into a large-bodied recipient giant danio to produce a suitable surrogate that can efficiently produce zebrafish gametes in a significantly higher amount than that of the donor. The systematic procedure of producing sterile giant danio was developed to ablate the endogenous germ cells completely. This study (Chapter 2) revealed the genetic compatibility of giant danio gonadal somatic cells to accommodate and nourish the germ cells from a species of different genera. Chapter 3 verified and strengthened our understanding, for the first time, of the epigenetic changes acquired by the donor germ cells and their possible inheritance to future generations. Since many studies now deal with germ cell transplantation in fish to assess or produce germline chimera, it is crucial to consider the donor's safety. Chapter 4 successfully developed an approach to harvest the testicular cells for transplantation in zebrafish with no mortality in the donor. This study (chapter 4) used smaller species (zebrafish and killifish) to conduct partial gonadectomy in order to show that big-body-sized species will be much more suitable for this experiment and can survive the procedure.

1. Germ cell compatibility and development in the xenogenic recipient

The success of germline chimera production between genetically distant species can be challenging for well-known reasons, such as the failure of transplanted germ cell coalescence with the supporting gonadal somatic cells of the recipient. The interaction seems simple when working with closely related species belonging to the same genera. The difficulty may arise as the genetic distance goes farther. Another factor is the degree of sterility in the host, as some methods, like triploidization and interspecific hybridization, do not entirely remove the endogenous germ cells. Germ cell development and proliferation are supported by the gonadal niche created by the supporting cells, Sertoli cells, and extracellular matrix (Schulz et al., 2010). The presence of even fewer endogenous germ cells may induce competition to retain in the supporting microenvironment, leading to the rejection of foreign germ cell incorporation and development. This section deals with various factors contributing to the success and failure of germ cell development in the xenogenic recipient post-transplantation.

Genetic compatibility

The rate of transplantation efficiency is comparatively higher at the species level than at the genus and family level. The incorporation of transplanted germ cells between the same species leads to low rejection because of their strong genetic compatibility. However, few studies have reported successful germline chimera production in recipients from different orders (Silva et al., 2016), families (Saito et al., 2008), subfamilies (Zhang et al., 2022), and genera (Morita et al., 2015; Hamasaki et al., 2017; Franěk et al., 2021; Nayak et al., 2023). There are studies that report no donor-derived production after xenogenic transplantation (Yazawa et al., 2010; Bar et al., 2016). The successful studies indicate that the germ-soma interaction may be conserved in some teleost, potentially supporting the proliferation of foreign germ cells. However, the efficiency or the number of germline chimera produced is relatively low, as observed in Chapter 2 with giant danio recipients. The interaction required for xenogenic germ-soma coalescence has never been explored experimentally and remains to be unveiled. In addition, the germ-soma interaction and their development is sometimes specific to the species. Gametogenesis is a highly coordinated process and cellular communication between developing germ cells and supporting somatic cells. The gap junction transmembrane protein connexins (Cxs) are reported to play a crucial role in cell-cell communication during every

stage of gametogenesis in the teleost (De Montgolfier et al., 2007). Notably, fish testis expresses a variety of Cxs (Cheng et al., 2004; De Montgolfier et al., 2007) that may be species-specific and facilitate germ cell development. Considering this, it can be assumed that cellular receptors and molecular factors are required to respond and interact with the transplanted germ cells, failing which leads to their rejection. To date, the only means to check the germ cell compatibility between the genetically distant species is to perform the germ cell transplantation assay.

Stemness of germ cell

The stemness of a germ cell can be described as the most undifferentiated state of its lineage. As the reports suggest, the germ cell with stemness can only colonize the recipient gonad post-transplantation (Ichida et al., 2019). Embryonic germ stem cells, PGCs, are highly pluripotent and can populate the host gonad from different genera and families (Ciruna et al., 2002; Saito et al., 2008, 2010). Xenogeneic germline chimera production is assumed to be highly efficient with PGC transplantation. However, this method is rarely successful due to the high mortality of host embryos post-transplantation and the skill-sensitiveness that requires delicate micromanipulation. Testicular cell suspensions isolated from the adults contain all stages of spermatogonia, such as proliferating/self-renewing, differentiating, and most differentiated. Reportedly, only SPG-A possesses the ability to incorporate into the empty gonad (Iwasaki-Takahashi et al., 2020). This phenomenon is well described in Chapter 2 with supporting results, as the total testicular suspension from zebrafish failed to colonize the giant danio gonad, but the cell enrichment with density gradient centrifugation (a method to selectively isolate cell population with lower density from the total cell suspension) potentially helped to generate germline chimera. However, the total testicular cell suspension was able to successfully colonize the recipient gonad in zebrafish intraspecific transplantation (transplantation was performed between different strains of zebrafish) (Franěk et al., 2019b, 2022). These reports clearly indicate that the stemness of germ cells potentially contributes to the efficiency of xenogenic transplantation. There are several techniques have developed for SPG-A enrichment, such as In vitro expansion of SPG-A through cell culture (Iwasaki-Takahashi et al., 2020), cell sorting using monoclonal antibodies (Ichida et al., 2019), and flow cytometry enrichment base on light scattering properties (Kise et al., 2012). Furthermore, germ cell stemness properties do not guarantee transplantation success between all distant species where the genetic compatibility factors are at play, but it is one of the essential factors to consider during germ cell isolation in order to improve efficiency.

Host sterility

The degree of host sterility substantially affects the incorporation of donor germ cells in xenogenic transplantation. The farther the phylogenetic distance between donor and recipient, the stronger the possibility of rejection post-transplantation. Complete removal of germ cell precursors during embryonic development using gene knockout or knockdown techniques is favorable for genetically distant recipients. Other recipients, such as triploids and interspecific hybrids, may outcompete the transplanted germ cells and lead to no or very low colonization rate of the donor germ cell. A study by Franěk et al. reported that the *dnd* knockdown recipients are more favorable than those produced by other methods (Franěk et al., 2022), as they offer empty niches that can accommodate only exogenous germ cells. The study performed in Chapter 3 reported that interspecific hybrid surrogates produced recipient-derived spermatozoa, which significantly decreased the fertilization rate of the donor-derived gametes, indicating the level of sterility is a crucial factor. Although it is hard to assess or assume the exogenous germ cell incorporation rate considering only the

degree of sterility, a constant factor, many other factors mentioned above can be a potential reason for transplantation failure.

2. Germ-soma interaction post-transplantation and their functional consequences

The interaction of introduced germ cells with the gonadal microenvironment of the recipient poses several questions on their practical application or reliability on surrogate broodstock propagation. Several successful studies have been reported for donor-derived gamete production via germline chimera, as apparent by several published studies. However, information on the journey of exogenous germ cells post-transplantation and their development has never been acquired. The study reported in Chapter 3 has provided new insight into scenarios underlying germ-soma interaction in the recipient gonad at the individual and species levels with possible molecular consequences. As shown in the supported literature (Chapter 3), the morphological variations were reported in a few studies in donor-derived gametes and progeny (Saito et al., 2008; Franěk et al., 2021) that draw our attention to the molecular changes underlying these phenotypes and their possible causes. Unlike genetic mutations, epigenetic modifications are more likely to occur due to environmental stress. It is known that epigenetic marks play a critical role in gene regulation and thereby control cellular functions. The surrogate production approach needs immediate attention regarding epigenetic modifications as they involve many systematic procedures where the donor germ cells are subjected to physical stressors, beginning from their isolation to gametogenesis in the recipient gonad. This thesis's primary goal was to address the compatibility of donor germ cells with recipient gonadal somatic cells, which also involves deciphering their interactions in a new microenvironment in different surrogate types. The DNA methylome comparison between the interspecific (xenogenic) and intraspecific (allogenic) chimera revealed many alterations, described thoroughly in Chapter 3. However, the observed changes in DNA methylation could not induce any phenotypical alterations in the F1 offspring. The discussion remains on whether there is a threshold of methylation density to give a phenotypical response that needs to be validated in future studies. In addition, this study involved recipients from the same species and the hybrids, where one parent is the same as the donor species. The effect of the recipient's gonadal microenvironment may not be drastic on the donor germ cells and their development. Moreover, the author would like to point out the limitation of the study reported in Chapter 3 on phenotypical analysis of the F1 progeny. Although the progenies did not show any severe malformations for *pcdh1g* promoter hypermethylation, a more comprehensive analysis of the micro phenotypical analysis on the F1 progenies derived from the intraspecific surrogate would have been beneficial to claim these findings. The lack of additional trait variability observation was because of the unavailability of living biological material due to a long gap between obtaining the methylome data and investigating phenotypical and behavioral analysis. However, our future study will cover the lack of in-depth phenotypical investigation on the donor-derived progeny.

Several reported studies where the recipients are from different genera (like in Chapter 2, Nayak et al., 2023) and families (Saito et al., 2008) will be interesting to dissect through their epigenetic remodelling. Knowing the DNA methylation arrangement before and after fertilization is essential to understand the epigenetic alterations in surrogate production. In zebrafish, the paternal methylation pattern is retained in the offspring post-fertilization. In contrast, the maternal pattern is discarded (Jiang et al., 2013), and they do not undergo epigenetic reprogramming like mammals (Skvortsova et al., 2019). On the contrary, another model species, medaka, quite resembles DNA methylation reprogramming in mammalian

embryogenesis, where the embryo undergoes epigenetic reprogramming and discard almost all paternal epigenetic marks (Wang and Bhandari, 2020). Unlike zebrafish, species like medaka are presumed to be less susceptible to carrying parental epigenetic marks post-fertilization as they undergo demethylation except for a few genes. This is why this study chose zebrafish to analyse the epimutation after surrogate production. This scenario can differ among species, requiring thorough phenotypic analysis in the donor-derived offspring. Also, the morphological characteristics of the donor-derived gametes must be compared with those of the donor before studying their epigenome. The most important finding from the studies carried out in Chapter 3 is that not all gene regulations are methylation-dependent. Alternatively, they may require a threshold of methylation density to induce any phenotypical changes in the progeny.

The changes resulting from the foreign germ-soma interaction may induce some aberrant alternation in the donor-derived gametes. However, whether their persistence is transient or permanent over generations is an essential question for future studies. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) is often used as a cryoprotectant for long-term germ cell preservation (Pšenička et al., 2016; Franěk et al., 2019a; Marinović et al., 2019). Notably, it can change cell fate decisions by inducing DNA methylation (Iwatani et al., 2006). Elucidating the molecular consequences of cryopreserved germ cell transplantation in the produced gametes and the offspring is the next stage of research to check their reliability. The observed results from this comparative study interpret many possible explanations: 1) Firstly, the transplanted cells undergo a natural selection where the damaged cells or cells with aberrant epigenetic makeup may not undergo proliferation and differentiation in the recipient's gonad, and the healthier cells proceed further, 2) or the opposite scenario could be that the cell with a newly gained epigenetic makeup caused by the recipient's gonadal microenvironment that survives only undergoes differentiation, and others die. In both cases, the consequences are worth knowing in order to understand the nature of transplanted germ cell and recipient gonadal somatic cell interactions.

3. Easing the germ cell isolation from the donors

It is highly unpredictable to expect the success of germline chimera production in the case of xenogenic germ cell transplantation. Surrogate production is a complex and time-consuming technique, and the success often depends on many factors besides the genetic relationship and host sterility. These failures lead to the repetition of the whole procedure that involves harvesting the fresh germ cells from the donor, involving sacrifice. This thesis developed a partial gonadectomy approach to isolate the donor testis by resection and suturing them back, as described in Chapter 4. In our study, partial gonadectomy proved non-lethal for the smallest species, zebrafish and killifish. This technique potentially offered an alternative approach to killing donors during germ cell isolation. The developed approach may substantially help some valuable species, like sturgeon, that take years to mature sexually and require intense care during rearing. Transgenic lines and the lines developed with genome editing technologies are valuable to lose. The gonadectomy in zebrafish and killifish did not compromise their reproductive output because the resected part of the testis was regenerated. This again provides another opportunity to use the same donor for germ cell isolation for surrogate production. In addition, this technique did not report any mortality in the gonadectomized individuals for both zebrafish and killifish.

4. Conclusions and future directions in germ cell transplantation

Germ cell transplantation technologies can potentially help genetic improvement in aquaculture, as proven by several successful studies mentioned in the above chapters. New tools and techniques are emerging with time, adding more potential to the surrogate broodstock technologies to work with genetically distant species. Speeding up the maturation period for species with long reproductive cycles with a surrogate with a shorter sexual maturation time may expedite the progeny production (Hattori et al., 2019). Similarly, the species threatened by diseases in their natural habitat and challenging to rear in captivity can be conserved using their germ cell transplantation in a suitable host. Although the success of xenotransplantation is low and the failure is often noticed, it tells us that immune compatibility is low when other factors are promising. Future studies must focus on the immunosystem profiling of the larvae or study the molecular factors involved in rejecting the gonial cell coalescence with somatic cells in distant species. Suppressing these factors by transient gene silencing during the window of germ cell incorporation until their complete occupancy in the recipient gonad may ease xenogenic transplantation. A thorough investigation of interactions between the receptor and ligand of germ cells and recipient gonadal somatic cells may provide insight into the failures. The studies performed in this thesis suggest that xenogenic transplantation from a smaller species into a bigger surrogate parent can efficiently solve the issue of low gamete production. The biotechnologies involving germ cell transplantation have an impact on the donor epigenome in the intraspecific (different strains of the same species) and interspecific germline chimera production (into the interspecific hybrids) that indicates that divergent species may have drastic changes on the donor-derived gametes and may keep this epigenetic memory in the future generations.

- The specific conclusions that are drawn from the studies this thesis reported are the following:
- Zebrafish spermatogonial cells show compatibility with the recipient giant danio from a different genus and can be successfully used as a surrogate to produce significantly higher amounts of sperm (Chapter 2).
- Giant danio follows a sex-determination system similar to zebrafish, developing into a mono-sex male population after germ cell depletion (Chapter 2).
- Donor-derived gametes from inter- and intraspecific surrogates present a globally hypermethylated genome compared to the donors. The observed hypermethylation showed no functional/phenotypical changes in the F1 progenies (Chapter 3).
- Protocadherin gamma promoters are found to be hypermethylated in donor-derived sperm and progeny from the intraspecific surrogate; however, the gene expression level remains unchanged (Chapter 3).
- Promoter hypermethylation in the MAPK/p53 pathway genes affects the removal of meiotic-arrested germ cells in the interspecific hybrid surrogate (Chapter 3).
- Partial gonadectomy is the alternative approach of germ cell harvesting from the donor without killing them and compromising their reproductive performance (Chapter 4).

This thesis has addressed the critical points in surrogate production technologies that provide new directions for future xenogenic germ cell transplantation studies. The successful gamete production enhancement using xenogenic transplantation allows the testing of other species with low fecundity. All the performed studies included in this Ph.D. dissertation are new and first reported in this field, be it boosting gamete production, investigating donor-derived gametes epigenome, or germ cell harvesting with a non-lethal protocol. Epigenetic alteration

influenced by germ cell transplantation is the first and novel in this field to be reported using zebrafish. The results obtained from this experiment open many questions on the studies performed in the past and possibly be reported in the future. Surrogate production between genetically distant species needs more attention and careful investigation to ensure that the techniques used do not disturb the normal cellular and molecular functions of the donor species. New studies will elucidate the perturbed epigenetic marks and their consequences using divergent species and the donor-derived gametes produced with cryopreserved germ stem cells. In addition, the cultured gonial cells and PGCs are some important candidates for possible epigenetic remodelling due to long-term culture using medium and growth factors. As this study described in Chapter 3 is the beginning of epigenetic explorations, the subsequent investigations will include verifying every technique involved in surrogate production technologies to know their practical reliability in research and commercial aquaculture.

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English summary**Study on the compatibility of germ cells after transplantation into a recipient***Rigolin Nayak*

Surrogate production by germline stem cell transplantation is new-age biotechnology to improve aquaculture and basic research pertaining to reproductive biology in fishes. Germ stem cells harvested from the donor at the embryonic or adult stage are transplanted into genetically compatible sterile recipients. The transplanted germ cells are less likely to be rejected by the recipient when the genetic relationship is at the species level. However, the germline chimera production decreases in the case of the phylogenetically distant species. Xenogenic transplantation is often targeted to improve certain traits in the donor species, such as speeding up sexual maturation time, removing the environmental barriers to captive rearing, preserving the genetic resources of threatened species, and boosting gamete production via surrogacy. Germ cell transplantation between those distant species often failed due to less genetic compatibility and other factors, such as the degree of sterility and the stemness of the transplanted germ cell. Another central question about surrogate production concerns the epigenetic changes in donor-derived gametes and progeny, which remain to be unveiled. Epimutations (loss or gain of DNA methylation) are known to cause functional changes that are heritable to many generations. DNA methylation is the best-studied epigenetic mark that regulates gene expression. The germ cells undergo several mechanical and enzymatic treatments during their isolation. Proliferation and differentiation are guided by the host gonadal somatic cells that undoubtedly differ from the donor gonadal microenvironment. Those changes can influence the methylome of the donor germline and, thereby, cause cellular and functional changes that may persist over generations. Xenogenic transplantation was performed between zebrafish and giant danio to increase the amount of zebrafish gametes via giant danio surrogates. The giant danio dead end (*dnd*) gene was sequenced, and morpholino sequences were designed to deplete germ cell development in giant danio effectively. Spermatogonial transplantation was optimized to produce giant danio germline chimera with ten times more concentrated zebrafish donor-derived sperm than the donor. A similar method can be applied to other species in the future to increase gamete production via a bigger surrogate. A thorough investigation of epimutations and their functional changes was assessed using two kinds of surrogates. The study revealed that the sperm and progeny from both surrogates are genome-wide hypermethylated compared to the donor sperm and progeny. The perturbed hypermethylation did not influence gene expression changes or phenotypical abnormalities confirmed by gene expression analyses and phenotypical investigations. Partial gonadectomy in two small species, zebrafish and killifish, provided an effective method for germ cell isolation without sacrificing the donor, which may apply to other species for surrogate production. The data from the current study will provide greater insight into future germ cell transplantation studies, and the epigenetic comparative studies set the stage for in-depth analysis of donor-derived gametes from phylogenetically distant surrogates and the cryopreserved germ stem cells.

Kryokonzervace rybího spermatu: kvalita versus kvantita*Rigolin Nayak*

Náhradní produkce pomocí transplantace zárodečných kmenových buněk je novou biotechnologií, která má zefektivnit akvakulturu a základní výzkum týkající se reprodukční biologie ryb. Zárodečné kmenové buňky odebrané dárce v embryonálním nebo dospělém stadiu se transplantují geneticky kompatibilním sterilním příjemcům. U transplantovaných zárodečných buněk je méně pravděpodobné, že budou příjemcem odmítnuty, pokud je genetická příbuznost na úrovni druhu. Produkce zárodečných chimér se však snižuje v případech fylogeneticky vzdálených druhů. Xenogenní transplantace je často zaměřena na zlepšení určitých vlastností dárcovského druhu, jako je zrychlení doby pohlavního dozrávání, odbourání environmentálních překážek při chovu v zajetí, zachování genetických zdrojů ohrožených druhů a zvýšení produkce gamet prostřednictvím náhradního rodičovství. Transplantace zárodečných buněk mezi těmito vzdálenými druhy často selhávala kvůli menší genetické kompatibilitě a dalším faktorům, jako je stupeň sterility a kmenovost transplantovaných zárodečných buněk. Další ústřední otázka zabývající se náhradní produkcí se týká epigenetických změn v gametách a potomstvu pocházejícím od dárce, které dosud nebyly zkoumány. Je známo, že epimutace (ztráta nebo získání metylace DNA) způsobují funkční změny, které jsou dědičné pro mnoho generací. Methylace DNA je nejlépe prozkoumanou epigenetickou značkou, která reguluje genovou expresi. Zárodečné buňky jsou během izolace podrobeny několika mechanickým a enzymatickým úpravám. Proliferace a diferenciací se řídí somatickými buňkami hostitelské gonády, které se nepochybně liší od mikroprostředí dárcovské gonády. Tyto změny mohou ovlivnit metylom dárcovské zárodečné linie, a tím způsobit buněčné a funkční změny, které mohou přetrvávat po generaci. Byla provedena xenogenní transplantace mezi zebříčkami a daniem malabarským s cílem zvýšit množství gamet zebříček prostřednictvím náhradních rodičů dania malabarského. Byl sekvenován *dean end* gen (*dnd*) dania malabarského a byly navrženy morfolinové sekvence, které účinně znemožňují vývoj zárodečných buněk. Transplantací spermatogonií vznikly zárodečné chiméry dania malabarského produkující spermie zebříčky, které byly desetkrát koncentrovanější než spermie dárce. Podobnou metodu lze v budoucnu použít i u jiných druhů ke zvýšení produkce gamet prostřednictvím většího náhradního rodiče. Pomocí dvou typů náhradních rodičů bylo provedeno podrobné zkoumání epimutací a jejich funkčních změn. Studie odhalila, že spermie a potomstvo obou náhradních rodičů jsou ve srovnání se spermii a potomstvem dárce hypermetylované v celém genomu. Porušená hypermethylace neměla vliv na změny genové exprese ani na fenotypové abnormality potvrzené analýzami genové exprese a fenotypovými vyšetřeními. Částečná gonadektomie u dvou malých druhů ryb, zebříček a halančíků, poskytla účinnou metodu izolace zárodečných buněk bez nutnosti usmrcení dárce, která se může uplatnit i u jiných druhů pro náhradní reprodukci. Údaje z této studie poskytnou lepší vhled do budoucích studií transplantace zárodečných buněk a epigenetické srovnávací studie otevírají prostor pro podrobnou analýzu gamet odvozených od dárce z fylogeneticky vzdálených náhradních spermií a kryokonzervovaných zárodečných kmenových buněk.

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List of publications

Peer-reviewed journals with IF

- Dey, A., **Nayak, R.**, Prchal, M., Gonzalez-Cid, A., Pšenička, M., Šindelka, R., Flajšhans, M., Gazo, I., 2024. Species-specific differences in DNA damage sensitivity at early developmental stage: A comparative study of sterlet (*Acipenser ruthenus*) and common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology* 110, 104501. (IF 2023 = 4.2)
- Cheng, Y., Zhang, S., **Nayak, R.**, Vechtová, P., Schumacher, F., Linhartová, P., Gazo, I., Linhartová, Z., Waghmare, S., Kleuser, B., Dey, A., Rodinová, V., Rodina, M., Sterba, J., Alavi, S., Labbé, C., Linhart, O., 2024. Fertilization by short-term stored sperm alters DNA methylation patterns in common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) embryos at single-base resolution. *Rev. Fish Biol. Fisheries*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11160-024-09866-y>. (IF 2023 = 5.9)
- Nayak, R.**, Franěk, R., Laurent, A., Pšenička, M., 2024. Genome-wide comparative methylation analysis reveals the fate of germ stem cells after surrogate production in teleost. *BMC Biology* 22, 39. (IF 2023 = 4.4)
- Nayak, R.**, Franěk, R., Šindelka, R., Pšenička, M., 2023. Enhancement of zebrafish sperm production via a large body-sized surrogate with germ cell transplantation. *Communications Biology* 6, 412. (IF 2022 = 5.9)

International conferences

- Nayak, R.**, Franěk, R., Laurent, A., Pšenička, M., 2024. Genome-wide comparative methylation analysis reveals the fate of germ stem cells after surrogate production in teleost. 9th international workshop on the biology of fish gametes. July 15–18, 2024, Leon, Spain. Oral presentation.
- Nayak, R.**, Pšenička, M., Franěk, R., 2024. Partial gonadectomy: A new approach to obtain germline stem cells for transplantation while preserving the donor. July 15–18, 2024, Leon, Spain. Oral presentation.
- Nayak, R.**, Franěk, R., Pšenička, M., 2023. Genome-wide comparative methylation analysis in zebrafish produced via surrogacy. 12th International Symposium on Reproductive Physiology of Fish. September 15–19, 2023, Crete, Greece. Oral presentation.
- Nayak, R.**, Franěk, R., Šindelka, R., Pšenička, M., 2022. Enhancement of zebrafish gamete production in a big body-sized giant danio by germ cell transplantation. 8th international workshop on the biology of fish gametes. September 20–23, 2022, Gdansk, Poland. Oral presentation.

Training and supervision plan during study

Name	Rigolin Nayak
Research department	Laboratory of Germ Cells
Supervisor	Assoc. Prof. Martin Pšenička
Period	July 2020 – September 2024
Ph.D. courses	
	Year
Applied hydrobiology	2021
Pond aquaculture	2021
Ichthyology and fish systematics	2021
Czech language	2022
English language	2022
Scientific seminars	
	Year
Seminar days of FFPW	2021
	2022
	2023
	2024
International conferences	
	Year
Nayak, R., Franěk, R., Šindelka, R., Pšenička, M., 2022. Enhancement of zebrafish gamete production in a big body-sized giant danio by germ cell transplantation. 8 th international workshop on the biology of fish gametes. September 20–23, 2022, Gdansk, Poland. Oral presentation	2022
Nayak, R., Franěk, R., Pšenička, M., 2023. Genome-wide comparative methylation analysis in zebrafish produced via surrogacy. 12 th International Symposium on Reproductive Physiology of Fish. September 15–19, 2023, Crete, Greece. Oral presentation	2023
Nayak, R., Franěk, R., Laurent, A., Pšenička, M., 2024. Genome-wide comparative methylation analysis reveals the fate of germ stem cells after surrogate production in teleost. 9 th international workshop on the biology of fish gametes. July 15–18, 2024, Leon, Spain. Oral presentation	2024
Nayak, R., Pšenička, M., Franěk, R., 2024. Partial gonadectomy: A new approach to obtain germline stem cells for transplantation while preserving the donor. July 15–18, 2024, Leon, Spain. Oral presentation	2024
Foreign stays during Ph.D. study at FFPW	
	Year
Laboratory of Fish Physiology and Genomics, INRAE, Rennes, France Supervisor – Dr Catherine Labbé	2023
Pedagogical activities	
	Year
Summer school 1 (cell fate mapping)	2021
Summer school 2 (Germ cell transplantation in zebrafish)	2024
Consultanat of Ph.D. thesis of Abhipsha Dey, M.Sc. entitled "Diverse role of DNA repair genes and proteins on fish embryo development."	2021–present

Curriculum vitae**PERSONAL INFORMATION**

Name: Rigolin
Surname: Nayak
Title: M.Sc.
Born: 05/05/1993
Nationality: Indian
Languages: Odia, Hindi (Native speaker), English (IELTS score 6.5)
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RESEARCH INTEREST

Reproductive biotechnology
 Germ stem cell manipulation and transplantation
 Epigenetic remodelling

EDUCATION

2020 – present Ph.D. student in Fishery, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia, České Budějovice, Czech Republic
2013–2015 M.Sc. Biotechnology, Berhampur University, Odisha, India
2010–2013 B.Sc. in Biotechnology, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

2020 – present Research student at Fishery, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia, České Budějovice, Czech Republic
December 2017 – May 2020 Research Associate at MedGenome Labs Ltd. Bangalore, India
March 2017 – May 2018 Junior researcher at Chromous Biotech Private Ltd. Bangalore, India

COMPLETED COURSES

Basics of scientific communication, Ichthyology and fish taxonomy, Pond aquaculture, English language

RESEARCH STAY

Foreign internship at Laboratory of Fish Physiology and Genomics, INRAE, Rennes, France
 Supervisor – Dr. Catherine Labbé